

Deliverable D1.5 – Catalogue of existing OS solutions – updated version

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Abstract:	<p>This document presents the second iteration of T1.2: Cataloguing of existing open-source (OS) software and open hardware solutions, providing an expanded and refined inventory to support sustainable and efficient agriculture. This update introduces new solutions covering key production steps such as fertilization, irrigation, pest management, and livestock management. Each entry now includes additional details on licensing, repository metrics, connectivity requirements, and technical specifications. Existing solutions have been reviewed and enhanced based on stakeholder feedback and updated evaluations of Technology Readiness Level (TRL), end-user profiles, production stages, and community engagement. This improved catalogue strengthens the foundation for the Decision Support Tool (DST), enabling stakeholders to make informed choices when selecting and adopting OS solutions.</p>

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Table 1: List of abbreviations and acronyms

List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	
ADS	Agricultural Digital Solutions
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
DG-Agri	Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development
DG-DIGIT	Directorate-General for Informatics
DG-DEFIS	Directorate-General for Defence Industry and Space
DG-Grow	Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship, and SMEs
DG-JRC	Directorate-General Joint Research Centre
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FMIS	Farm Management Information System
GIS	Geographic Information System
GSOD	Global Surface Summary of the Day
HE	Horizon Europe
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IoT	Internet of Things
OS	Open Source
OSGEO	Open Source Geospatial Foundation
POSCAS	Parametric Open Source Cold-Frame Agrivoltaic Systems
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WP	Work Package

Disclaimer

While every effort has been made to accurately record the licensing status and all other information presented, this catalogue is provided for informational purposes only. Users are strongly encouraged to verify these details—particularly the license terms and conditions—before adopting or integrating any solution, and to take special care when no explicit license is listed in the repository. The partners of the OpenAgri project make no representations or warranties of any kind, express or implied about the completeness, accuracy, reliability or suitability with respect to the interactive catalogue or the information, products, services or related graphics contained in the catalogue for any purpose. Any reliance you place on such material is therefore strictly at your own risk.

Executive Summary

This document advances the effort to democratize digital farming by presenting the second iteration of the catalogue of open-source (OS) software and open hardware-based Agricultural Digital Solutions (ADSs). Building on the first version, this iteration expands and refines the inventory, offering updated, more detailed information to better support farmers, advisors, developers, and policymakers in identifying and implementing open-source solutions tailored to their operational, technical, and environmental needs.

The updated catalogue introduces new solutions addressing key agricultural production steps, including fertilization, irrigation, pest management, and livestock management. In addition, the descriptions of all existing solutions have been reviewed and updated to ensure greater clarity, accuracy, and relevance. Each entry now includes additional information on licensing, repository metrics, connectivity requirements, alongside updated evaluations of Technology Readiness Level (TRL), end-user type, production stage, community engagement, and deployment scenarios. This enriched documentation enables more informed decision-making and supports the selection of solutions suited to diverse farming contexts and technological environments.

The catalogue now comprises 170 open-source solutions, including 132 open-source software ADSs and 38 open hardware-based ADSs. These solutions offer practical tools to enhance productivity, sustainability, and resilience across diverse agricultural systems.

The solutions cover edge, cloud, and hybrid deployment models, ensuring flexibility and adaptability across diverse technological environments and connectivity conditions. This user-oriented approach tailors information to the needs of farmers, advisors, developers, and policymakers, supporting the selection and implementation of the most suitable ADSs. Furthermore, the catalogue serves as a key resource for the ongoing development of the OpenAgri Decision Support Tool, helping stakeholders identify the best solutions for specific contexts and improving decision-making processes in agriculture.

This deliverable is closely interconnected with other project outputs, ensuring a cohesive and integrated approach to developing ADSs. The socio-economic and biogeographic data collected in D1.1 and the ongoing D1.2 provide essential context for understanding the environments in which these OS solutions can be deployed. Insights from the catalogue directly inform the development of the OpenAgri Decision Support Tool, contributing to more effective, sustainable agricultural practices across Europe. The interactive catalogue will continue to evolve, incorporating new findings, updates, and user feedback to maintain its relevance and utility. Ongoing collaboration with global open-source communities and agricultural networks will further enrich the catalogue, fostering innovation and practical applications in digital farming.

1. Introduction

1.1. Project summary

The overall aim of the OpenAgri project is to democratize digital farming by enabling the development and deployment of innovative cost-effective energy-efficient OS software and open hardware-based ADSs that can operate at a high performance even in remote areas with weak connectivity. This will be achieved by a) ensuring the co-creation of ADSs by engaging farmers and farm advisors in participatory prototyping activities inspired by the proliferation of makerspaces and fablabs; and b) providing access to a number of reusable OS software services designed to support the edge and mixed computing mode, and a “sociotechnical infrastructure”.

Using a multi-actor approach, OpenAgri will involve farmers, ADSs providers, farm advisors and scientists in 14 Sustainable Innovation Pilots (SIPs) in ≥ 10 countries across Europe, and guide them in co-creating and piloting edge, cloud and mixed-model ADSs addressing important challenges of agricultural production. 5 SIPs have been pre-selected and 9 more will be awarded through an Open Call, enabling a dynamic response to a changing policy and technology landscape. Finally, building on a thorough analysis of EU agriculture and the results from the SIPs, OpenAgri will create a Decision Support Tool that will allow Policy Makers, Farmers and Farm Advisors to select the best possible cloud, edge or mixed ADSs for any given set of conditions.

1.2. Document scope

This second iteration presents an expanded, refined, and enriched inventory of open-source (OS) software and open hardware-based solutions for agriculture. Building on the initial version, this updated deliverable integrates newly identified solutions, incorporates additional metadata fields such as licensing, repository metrics, and connectivity requirements, and provides revised descriptions of existing entries to improve clarity, accuracy, and relevance. In addition to expanding its content, this iteration enhances the catalogue’s usability for a broad range of stakeholders. It includes solutions ready for immediate implementation by farmers and advisors, as well as components and tools valuable to developers and AgriTech providers for creating or improving ADSs. Each entry offers updated information on Technology Readiness Level (TRL), intended end-user, targeted agricultural production step, community engagement, deployment scenarios across edge, cloud, and hybrid models, alongside the new metadata fields.

While the first iteration of the catalogue focused on mapping a broad landscape of existing open-source solutions, this second iteration emphasized depth, refinement, and applicability. Identifying additional relevant solutions has become increasingly challenging, as many widely known tools were already captured early on. However, substantial effort was dedicated to locating newer and more specialized solutions in underrepresented areas, and—importantly—reviewing and updating all existing entries. This included the integration of new technical fields such as licensing, connectivity requirements, and community engagement metrics. As a result, the second iteration represents not just a numerical expansion, but a qualitative improvement in the catalogue’s accuracy, usability, and readiness to support the Decision Support Tool (DST) and broader OpenAgri objectives.

By extending the scope and depth of the initial catalogue, this deliverable reinforces its role as both a standalone resource and a foundational input for the broader project ecosystem. It directly informs the development of the OpenAgri Decision Support Tool (Deliverables D1.7 and D1.8), guiding farmers, advisors, policymakers, and public administrators in selecting appropriate solutions tailored to specific operational, environmental, social and technological contexts. It remains closely integrated with socio-economic and

biogeographic insights from Deliverables D1.1, D1.2, and D1.3, ensuring its relevance across diverse agricultural settings.

This deliverable contributes to WP3 Pilots by incorporating open-source components developed through the Sustainable Innovation Pilots (SIPs), ensuring the catalogue reflects both existing solutions and emerging innovations. In addition, the catalogue offers a curated selection of open-source solutions that the pilots can draw from, adopt, or integrate into their own developments, supporting experimentation and practical application within pilot activities.

Moreover, the exploitation strategies outlined in WP4, particularly Task T4.1, continue to leverage the catalogue to maximize its visibility and impact. The dissemination, exploitation, and communication plan integrates the catalogue to promote broad stakeholder engagement across multiple channels. Following the publication of the interactive catalogue from the first iteration on the OpenAgri website, this second iteration now replaces it with an expanded, updated version. The interactive catalogue enables users to explore and filter solutions by various criteria such as Technology Readiness Level (TRL), end-user type, agricultural production step, licensing, and connectivity requirements, enhancing usability and relevance for diverse stakeholders. This alignment across deliverables ensures that the OS solutions identified and documented are not only technically robust but also practically applicable, supporting the adoption of effective, sustainable agricultural practices throughout Europe.

1.3. Document structure

This deliverable is organized to present the updated catalogue of Open Source Software and Open Hardware ADSs in a clear and systematic manner, supporting both internal project development and external stakeholder use.

Chapter 1 provides an overview of the OpenAgri project and outlines the scope and objectives of Deliverable D1.5, emphasizing its role in supporting the development of the Decision Support Tool (DST).

Chapter 2 presents the rationale behind updating the catalogue and details the methodological improvements made in this iteration, including refined selection criteria, new data fields, and enhanced documentation processes.

Chapter 3 contains the core content of the catalogue. It includes all tables and descriptive profiles of the identified OS solutions—software and hardware—organized by type and agricultural production step. This chapter also provides updated metadata such as TRL, end-user type, connectivity requirements, licensing information, and community metrics.

Chapter 4 describes the development and ongoing enhancement of the interactive catalogue hosted on the OpenAgri website. It outlines how the new data has been integrated and discusses future plans for its dissemination, use, and alignment with the project's DST and milestone objectives.

Chapter 5 offers concluding remarks, summarizing key findings from this iteration and identifying priorities for the next updates to the catalogue.

Chapter 6 lists all references cited throughout the document.

This structure ensures that the deliverable is comprehensive, accessible, and aligned with the broader goals of the OpenAgri project.

1.4. Decision Support Tool key modules and ADS knowledge base

The Decision Support Tool (DST) is being developed as an integrated platform to assist different stakeholders in identifying, selecting, and combining Agricultural Digital Solutions (ADSs) tailored to their specific needs, contexts, and goals. Central to the DST is the ADS catalogue produced in Task 1.2, which serves as the primary knowledge base, providing a detailed, continuously updated repository of open-source software and hardware solutions. By linking this catalogue with complementary data from Task 1.1—including geographical similarity indexes, rural connectivity indexes, and ADS needs indexes—the DST offers data-driven, targeted guidance to its users. The DST development plan includes three distinct modules so far, each designed to address the needs of a specific user group: farmers and farm advisors, policy makers and municipalities, and developers.

The farmer and farm advisor module is designed to help users select the most suitable ADSs for their farms by considering their production goals and directions, regional characteristics, and available infrastructure. The underlying knowledge base for this module combines the geographical similarity and rural connectivity indexes developed in Task 1.1 with the ADS catalogue from Task 1.2. Users begin by determining the scope of the requested advisory, entering the types of crops or livestock they manage and the agricultural production steps they wish to address, such as pest management or fertilization. They also indicate their farm's general location by selecting the relevant NUTS3 region. Using this information, the DST employs similarity analysis techniques to identify solutions that have been implemented in regions with comparable environmental and socio-economic characteristics. A connectivity assessment then evaluates the region's digital infrastructure to determine whether edge, cloud, or hybrid solutions are most appropriate. Finally, the DST filters and prioritizes relevant solutions from the ADS catalogue and the user with a tailored list of options that align with their specific needs and local conditions. Through this process, the ADS catalogue acts as a dynamic repository, enabling personalized and context-aware recommendations for farmers and advisors.

The policy maker and municipality module focuses on supporting decision-makers in understanding the ADS needs of specific regions and identifying appropriate solutions to address them. This module draws on multiple data sources, including the ADS needs indexes for fertilization, irrigation, pest management, and livestock developed in Task 1.1, the rural connectivity index, predominant crop types, and the ADS catalogue. Users begin by selecting their area of interest at a regional scale. The DST responds by identifying and displaying the area's predominant crop types. It then performs an ADS needs assessment to determine the region's demand for different types of solutions, alongside a connectivity assessment to evaluate digital infrastructure readiness. The DST presents a summary of needs and conditions, guiding policymakers in identifying priority areas for action. In addition to mapping needs, the DST connects these insights with existing solutions from the ADS catalogue, offering a curated list of relevant tools that could be adopted or promoted within the region. In this module, the catalogue not only provides a list of technologies but anchors them within a regional analysis to support informed policy and investment decisions.

The developer module is tailored to technical users seeking to design or enhance ADSs by combining or incorporating existing open-source components. Its knowledge base includes the geographical similarity indexes from Task 1.1 and the ADS catalogue, with a focus on individual components such as weather data services, geospatial platforms, visualization tools, and IoT integration components. Developers specify their target crops or livestock, the production steps they aim to support, and their area of interest. The DST then performs a similarity analysis to determine applicable environmental and socio-economic contexts. It identifies and presents relevant existing models and training datasets, highlights available supporting services, and suggests IoT integration components that align with the project goals. In this way, the ADS

catalogue functions as a repository of modular building blocks, enabling developers to assemble tailored solutions that meet specific agricultural challenges while leveraging existing resources.

Across all three modules, the ADS catalogue is the central knowledge resource powering the DST's recommendation engine. Its detailed documentation of each solution—including technical readiness, licensing, deployment models, connectivity requirements, end-user focus, and production stage—ensures that the DST can deliver sufficiently documented, technically valid, contextually relevant, and practically applicable guidance. The second iteration of the catalogue, now available as an interactive tool on the OpenAgri website, further enhances this role by offering users advanced filtering options and continuously updated content. By integrating this evolving knowledge base, the DST provides a flexible, data-driven platform to support the adoption, design, and promotion of open-source digital solutions in agriculture.

1.5. Key Updates from the 1st Iteration

1.5.1. Refinements Based on DST co-creation feedback

The second iteration of the ADS catalogue has been shaped by an ongoing, collaborative process within the consortium, involving continuous discussions, feedback loops, and iterative improvements. Throughout the development of the Decision Support Tool (DST), multiple consortium meetings provided a platform to align the catalogue's content and structure with the evolving needs of different stakeholder groups. This collaborative process culminated in a dedicated DST co-creation meeting, where an initial mock-up of the DST was presented to partners to gather targeted feedback and insights. A key outcome of these discussions was the recognition of the need to expand the catalogue with more complete solutions across diverse agricultural production steps. Partners highlighted the importance of ensuring sufficient coverage of areas such as fertilization, irrigation, pest management, and livestock management, so that the DST could support users in addressing a broader set of challenges across the agricultural value chain. In response, the second iteration actively incorporated new solutions in these categories, improving both the scope and practical relevance of the catalogue.

In parallel, the co-creation process reinforced the importance of documenting simpler, modular components—such as data services, geospatial platforms, visualization tools, and IoT integration modules—that could be recombined by developers to create customized solutions. This perspective broadened the role of the catalogue from a static list of ready-made tools to a dynamic resource that also supports innovation and solution design. Further refinements were introduced to enhance the catalogue's technical completeness and usability. Based on feedback from partners, additional metadata fields were incorporated, including licensing information and connectivity requirements for each solution. These additions enable the DST to better assess the technical and regulatory feasibility of solutions within different regions and deployment contexts.

The catalogue's evolution reflects a shared commitment within the consortium to ensure that it meets the diverse needs of farmers, advisors, developers, and policymakers. The collaborative approach—through ongoing meetings, iterative reviews, and the co-creation meeting with a simplified DST mock-up—continues to guide the catalogue's refinement, ensuring it remains a relevant, usable, and foundational knowledge base for the DST and the broader project.

1.5.2. Added Data Fields: Connectivity Requirements and Dependencies

In the second iteration of the ADS catalogue, a key enhancement was the inclusion of a new data field capturing the connectivity requirements and dependencies of each solution. While the first iteration already

classified solutions broadly as cloud-based, edge-based, or hybrid (mixed) models, feedback from the consortium identified the need for greater granularity and more descriptive insights into how each solution manages connectivity. To address this, the new data field not only assigns each solution to a connectivity category (None, Minimal, Medium, Maximum) but also provides supplementary details explaining the nature of the connectivity dependency, such as whether internet access is required continuously or periodically, or if cloud services are essential for specific functionalities. This richer layer of information equips users—particularly farmers, advisors, and developers—with a more nuanced understanding of technical feasibility in varying connectivity environments, enhancing the catalogue’s value as a decision-making tool.

To populate this field, each solution in the catalogue was reviewed individually, with detailed examination of its official documentation and source code repositories. This process allowed the consortium to classify each solution’s connectivity requirements according to four qualitative levels: None, Minimal, Medium, and Maximum. These categories reflect the degree of internet dependency for core functionality, ongoing operation, and data exchange between edge devices and cloud services.

By explicitly documenting this information, the catalogue empowers users to evaluate whether a solution is compatible with the connectivity conditions of their specific environment. For the DST, this data field plays an integral role in filtering and prioritizing solutions based on regional connectivity performance, as determined by the connectivity indexes developed in Task 1.1. Ultimately, this refinement strengthens the catalogue’s usability as a practical tool for selecting not only functionally relevant solutions, but also technically deployable ones under real-world infrastructure constraints.

1.5.3. Expanded Focus: Complete solutions

The second iteration of the ADS catalogue builds on the foundation established in the first version by expanding its coverage of complete, ready-to-use solutions across key agricultural production steps. While the initial catalogue already included several complete solutions, it became clear that further broadening this category was essential to ensure that the Decision Support Tool (DST) could offer deployable, practical options aligned with users’ operational needs. This iteration prioritized the identification and inclusion of additional complete solutions specifically targeting critical processes such as pest management, irrigation, fertilization, and livestock management. As a result, the catalogue now includes additionally, 9 open-source software solutions for pest management, 18 for irrigation, 9 for fertilization, and 9 for livestock management, alongside 9 additional open hardware-based solutions. This expanded coverage strengthens the catalogue’s capacity to support the DST in providing actionable, context-relevant recommendations for farmers, advisors, and policymakers. By complementing its existing collection of modular components with a broader range of integrated solutions, the catalogue ensures it can meet diverse user needs—offering both flexible building blocks for developers and ready-to-deploy tools for direct adoption in agricultural operations.

1.5.4. Additional Insights: Open-Source Licensing and Community Engagement

An important enhancement in the second iteration of the ADS catalogue was the inclusion of additional metadata to provide deeper insights into the licensing conditions and community engagement associated with each open-source solution. Given that licensing and community activity are critical factors for the adoption, adaptation, and sustainability of open-source tools, this iteration aimed to expand the catalogue’s coverage of these aspects, providing users with a more comprehensive understanding of each solution’s context. Each solution now includes, where available, information on its open-source license type, clarifying

the permissions and restrictions governing its use, modification, and redistribution. While licensing details were accessible for many solutions, this information was not consistently documented across all repositories; in cases where no license could be confirmed, this has been clearly noted to ensure transparency and alert users to potential limitations.

In addition to licensing, this iteration introduced new quantitative community engagement metrics, such as the number of forks and the date of the last commit retrieved from GitHub and similar platforms. These indicators complement the community engagement categorization introduced in the first iteration, which classified solutions as low, high, or very high based on the number of stars. By adding more granular repository metrics, the catalogue provides a richer, multidimensional view of community involvement, helping users better assess the maturity, maintenance status, and collaborative activity surrounding each solution.

Together, these insights enhance the catalogue's value as a decision-support resource, allowing users to evaluate not only technical suitability but also legal conditions and community sustainability when selecting open-source solutions.

1.5.5. Extended Solutions description & updated characteristics

One of the key updates in this second iteration of the ADS catalogue was the comprehensive extension and refinement of solution descriptions and associated characteristics. For all solutions carried over from the first iteration, the descriptions were expanded to include not only general overviews but also more detailed technical information. This enhancement ensures that users can better understand not just the purpose and applications of each solution, but also its underlying functionalities, system requirements, and integration potential. In addition to the enriched descriptions, all existing variables from the first iteration were systematically reviewed and updated. These include end-user categories, targeted agricultural production steps, crop or livestock focus, organizational type, Technology Readiness Level (TRL), and the deployment model (edge, cloud, or hybrid). Updating these variables across the entire catalogue has improved the consistency, accuracy, and relevance of the dataset, providing users with more reliable and up-to-date information for decision-making.

2. Overview

2.1. Rationale and Significance

Deliverable D1.5 – Catalogue of Existing OS Solutions – Updated Version represents an important advancement in the OpenAgri project, building on the foundation laid in the initial catalogue to further support the development of the DST for a wide range of end-users, including policymakers, farm advisors, farmers, developers, and public administrators. The central aim of this deliverable is to provide a robust, expanded, and continuously refined knowledge base that enables the selection of the most appropriate edge-, cloud-, or hybrid-based Open Source Agricultural Digital Solutions (OS ADSs), tailored to specific biogeographic, socio-economic, and infrastructural contexts.

This updated deliverable directly advances the overarching mission of OpenAgri: the democratization of digital farming. By significantly broadening and enriching the catalogue, this version ensures that a diverse set of open-source solutions—including both complete tools and modular components—are accessible to a wider audience, supporting equitable access to digital technologies and driving innovation, sustainability, and resilience in agriculture across Europe.

The rationale for creating and updating this catalogue is to empower end-users with reliable, actionable information for making informed decisions about agricultural digitalization. By systematically identifying and documenting existing OS solutions, the project helps avoid duplication of effort, highlights proven and effective technologies, and enables stakeholders to concentrate resources on deploying solutions with demonstrated success. This updated version also strengthens the integration between the catalogue and the biogeographic and socio-economic framing conditions analysed in Deliverables D1.1 & D1.2 ensuring that the solutions presented are contextually relevant and aligned with the real-world conditions and challenges faced across regions.

Importantly, this deliverable goes beyond compiling a list of available software and hardware. It provides rich, detailed profiles of each solution—including Technology Readiness Level (TRL), intended end-user, targeted agricultural production step, licensing, connectivity requirements, community engagement metrics, and deployment models—offering stakeholders critical insights for evaluating technical fit, feasibility, and potential impact. This expanded and more granular information lays the foundation for the DST, transforming the catalogue into an active, decision-support resource that can guide the adoption and deployment of tailored digital solutions.

The significance of Deliverable D1.5 extends to its role in fostering a dynamic, interactive, and continuously evolving platform. As the catalogue grows, it will remain a key enabler of the OpenAgri vision, promoting the uptake of innovative, open-source agricultural technologies and advancing the transition toward more efficient, sustainable, and resilient farming systems throughout Europe.

2.2. Methodology

2.2.1. Selection Criteria

The selection criteria for identifying and cataloguing existing OS software and open hardware-based solutions in this updated iteration were designed to ensure the inclusion of solutions that are relevant, functional, and aligned with the evolving needs of the OpenAgri project and the DST. The primary focus of this second iteration was to expand the catalogue with additional solutions, particularly in underrepresented agricultural production steps such as fertilization, irrigation, pest management, and livestock management. The goal was

to strengthen the catalogue's coverage with more complete, ready-to-use solutions, alongside modular components, to ensure the DST can provide actionable and context-specific recommendations to end-users. The main selection criterion continued to be the open-source nature of the solutions, with a strong preference for solutions available in open repositories with publicly accessible code or documentation. This approach ensures transparency, reproducibility, and the potential for ongoing community-driven improvement. In a small number of cases, however, the catalogue includes solutions that are publicly presented or promoted as open-source but for which no active repository could be located. These were added selectively when they were considered highly relevant or widely referenced in the agricultural innovation ecosystem, and they are clearly flagged in the catalogue to ensure transparency. As in the initial iteration, each solution was also assessed on several additional dimensions. These included its TRL, in order to maintain a balanced mix of mature and emerging solutions; its intended end-users, ensuring relevance for farmers, advisors, developers, and researchers; and its targeted agricultural production steps, with a particular focus on those areas identified as priorities for this update. Community support and engagement were evaluated not only through qualitative assessment but also by incorporating quantitative repository metrics, such as the number of forks, stars, and the date of the last commit. The catalogue also considers the applicability of solutions across edge, cloud, and hybrid deployment models, ensuring flexibility under varying technological and connectivity conditions. Finally, relevance and demonstrated effectiveness in agricultural contexts remained key, with attention given to solutions that have shown success in addressing real-world challenges.

2.2.2. Data Collection & Documentation

For this updated catalogue, the data collection process focused on expanding the coverage of agricultural production steps and improving the completeness and depth of documentation. A targeted literature review was conducted to identify digital solutions in specific areas such as fertilization, irrigation, pest management, and livestock management, with particular attention to evaluating their data availability and technical maturity. In addition to the literature review, systematic searches using targeted keywords were carried out on GitHub to identify new open-source software solutions and assess repository activity. This approach enabled the team to capture up-to-date insights into solution development, including repository metrics such as the number of forks and the date of the last commit. For open hardware solutions, the catalogue update focused primarily on FarmHack, a key source of grassroots, farmer-developed technologies, and expanded to include the Certified Open Source Hardware Projects listed on the OSHWA (Open Source Hardware Association) platform. This ensured the inclusion of rigorously documented and widely recognized open hardware initiatives. Newly collected data were documented to strengthen the catalogue's value as a decision-support resource. This iteration placed particular emphasis on adding connectivity requirements and licensing information, as well as expanding community engagement insights with repository-level metrics. Direct links to repositories, project websites, and supporting resources were included to facilitate further exploration and potential adoption by users.

3. Open Source Software & Open hardware based Agricultural Digital Solutions

3.1. Updates Overview

This updated version of the ADS catalogue presents a unified and substantially expanded overview of open-source software and open hardware solutions, reflecting the progress and refinements made in the second iteration. The catalogue now features a total of 170 open-source solutions (from a total of 104 in the previous version), including 134 software-based solutions and 38 open hardware-based solutions, covering a wide range of agricultural production steps, crop and livestock types, and deployment models (edge, cloud, and hybrid).

A key focus of this iteration was to broaden the catalogue with more complete solutions (table 2) addressing critical agricultural areas such as fertilization, irrigation, pest management, and livestock management. For example, in pest management, new entries like Wadhvani AI Pest Management and Smart Agricultural Pest Management System provide integrated monitoring and detection systems that use artificial intelligence and sensor data to help farmers reduce crop loss. In irrigation, solutions such as RoboRiego IoT Irrigation System, Automated Irrigation System, and Pirrigo deliver cloud- and edge-based automation and monitoring tools that allow farmers to optimize water use and improve sustainability. Livestock management and monitoring also received important additions, with tools like Pig Weight Estimation (Pixel Occupancy Analysis) and KAMADHENU, offering farmers low-cost, replicable tools to monitor animal growth, health, and environmental conditions. In fertilization, solutions like AgroNest and CropFusionAI combine nutrient management with data-driven decision support to improve input efficiency and environmental outcomes.

Beyond complete solutions, this iteration also maintains and updates a range of simpler/modular farm management components (table 3) and components focused on IoT integration, data processing, and analytics (table 4), crucial building blocks that enable the creation of customized digital solutions. Tools such as Eclipse Zenoh for efficient data exchange across IoT devices, Fiware Wilma for IoT device management, and InfluxDB for time-series data analytics remain essential components for precision farming. These modules can be combined to form powerful integrated systems: for example, a farmer could use FarmOS or OpenAgri Farm Calendar as the farm management backbone, connect it to Eclipse Zenoh for real-time sensor data collection, and integrate InfluxDB for historical data analysis and predictive insights. This modular approach ensures flexibility, scalability, and the ability to tailor solutions to specific farm conditions and goals.

A project example for the combination of these simpler/modular components is SIP3. In the development of the SIP3 ADS for detecting Colorado beetles using drone imagery, several open-source components from the provided software catalogue were integrated. The DJI Payload SDK is going to be used to interface directly with a DJI drone, giving access to important data such as location, battery status, and flight information. Communication between the edge device (a Raspberry Pi) and the cloud server is handled through Mosquitto MQTT, enabling efficient data exchange. Data processing workflows are going to be created and managed using the Ryax engine. To monitor system performance, runtime statistics are collected in InfluxDB and visualized with Grafana. Image metadata and detection results are stored in a PostgreSQL database, while the images themselves are saved using MinIO, a scalable object storage system. The final detection outcomes are presented through an interactive Streamlit web application, providing users with a clear and accessible interface.

The open hardware segment (table 5) was also expanded with nine new hardware solutions, strengthening the catalogue's support for farmer-led innovation and low-cost, replicable tools. Sourced primarily from

github, platforms like [FarmHack](#) and the [Certified Open Source Hardware Projects \(OSHWA\)](#), these devices include automated irrigation controllers, environmental monitoring sensors, and precision livestock farming tools. Examples include open hardware-based irrigation systems that automate water delivery based on soil moisture readings, compost monitoring sensors that help optimize organic fertilizer production, and cow heat detection systems that improve livestock reproduction management. These hardware solutions often complement software components by providing the physical interface for data collection and actuation in the field. By combining complete solutions, modular software components, and open hardware devices, the catalogue offers a versatile ecosystem of tools that stakeholders can use to meet diverse agricultural needs. For instance, an integrated solution for precision irrigation could combine a soil moisture sensor from the open hardware catalogue, Eclipse Zenoh for real-time data transmission, FarmOS for centralized farm management, and InfluxDB for analytics—creating a seamless pipeline from field sensing to data-driven decision-making.

Overall, this unified and enriched catalogue provides stakeholders with an unprecedented range of open-source solutions, each thoroughly documented with technical details, end-user profiles, agricultural application, licensing, community engagement, and connectivity requirements. This depth of information ensures that the solutions are not only technically feasible but also practically deployable, empowering farmers, advisors, developers, and policymakers to advance sustainable and resilient agricultural practices. The catalogue also forms the essential knowledge base for the OpenAgri Decision Support Tool, enabling tailored, context-sensitive recommendations across Europe’s diverse agricultural landscape.

Table 2: Open Source Software Complete Agricultural Digital Solutions

ADS	COUNTRY (information of current pilots/ mostly universal replicability)	END-USER	AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION STEP	CROP/LIVESTOCK	ORGANIZATION	TRL	EDGE/CLOUD/MIXED	URL	Community Engagement	Number of forks	Last commit	License
FaST	Spain/Italy/Estonia	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Fertilization	Crops	DG DEFIS/DG DIGIT/European Commission's DG Agriculture and Rural Development	7-8	Cloud	https://gitlab.com/fastplatform	Low			MIT license
Farm Advisory Tool for Nutrients (SATIVUM) DSS/Agri-environmental Monitoring for wheat in Mediterranean region	Spain	Farmers/ Advisors	Fertilization	Wheat	Quantifarm project	7	Mixed	https://www.sativum.es/web/sativum/tutorials				Public platform/ No source code available
Agstack Field Carbon model	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Fertilization	Crops	Linux Foundation	5	Cloud	https://github.com/agstack/field-carbon-model	High	0	2024-03-13	Apache 2.0 license
Fertilizer-Management-System	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors	Fertilization	Crops	GitHub user	4-5	Edge	https://github.com/W-P-N/Fertilizer-Management-System	Low	0	2023-06-10	Public Code, No license specified
Fertilizer Distribution Management System	Universal	Advisors (Municipalities, Agricultural Officers)	Fertilization	Crops	GitHub user	5	Edge	https://github.com/chamathamarsinghe96/Fertilizer-Distribution-Management-System	Low	6	2021-07-17	Public Code, No license specified
Harvestify	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Fertilization	Crops	GitHub user	7-8	Cloud	https://github.com/GladiaTor07/Harves	Very High			GPL-3.0

Crop Management System	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors	Fertilization	Crops	GitHub user	6-7	Edge	https://github.com/ab007shetty/crop-management-system	Low	10	2023-05-07	MIT	
CropFusionAI	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Fertilization	Crops	GitHub user	6-7	Cloud	https://github.com/deepe shdm/CropFusionAI	Low	3	2023-03-22	Public Code, No license specified	
AgriGo	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Fertilization/ Pest management	Crops	GitHub user	6-7	Cloud	https://github.com/kaymen99/AgriGo	Low	5	2024-11-21	MIT license	
Eco-fertilization	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Fertilization	Crops	GitHub user	5-6	Edge	https://github.com/Gekko12/Eco-fertilization	Low	8	2022-12-01	Public Code, No license specified	
Agromatic	Universal	Developers/ Researchers	Fertilization	Crops	GitHub user	5-6	Edge	https://github.com/nicolapace/agromatic	Low	3	2025-04-08	Public Code, No license specified	
AgroNest	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Fertilization	Crops	GitHub user	5-6	Cloud	https://github.com/VeenathT/AgroNest	Low	3	2024-05-14	Public Code, No license specified	
AgIoT	Portugal	Farmers/ Developers/ Researchers	Irrigation/ Fertilization/ Pest management	Mediterranean woody crops (apples, olives, Grapes)	Smart Farming project & Water4Ever project	6	Mixed	https://agiot.inesctec.pt/index.php/agiot-solution/	Low			Listed as Open Source, source code not found	
Agstack Pest models	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Pest management	Crops	Linux Foundation	5	Cloud	https://github.com/agstack/pest-models	Low	0	2021-10-15	GPL-3.0 license	

OpenWeedLocator	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Weed control	Crops	GitHub user	7	Cloud	https://github.com/geeza-coleman/OpenWeedLocator	Very high	67	2025-04-24	MIT license
Insect Detect	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors	Pest management	Crops	GitHub user	6-7	Mixed	https://github.com/maxsitt/insect-detect	High	20	2025-04-16	GPL-3.0 license
Wadhvani AI Pest Management	India-focused	Farmers	Pest management	Cotton	Wadhvani Institute for Artificial Intelligence	7-8	Mixed	https://github.com/WadhvaniAI/pest-management-opendata	low	0	2024-10-14	Apache-2.0 license
Insect Detection on Sticky Traps	Universal	Developers	Pest Management	Crops	GitHub user	5-6	Edge	https://github.com/checol-ag/insect-detection-scripts	Low	0	2025-02-21	Public Code, No license specified
Smart Agricultural Pest Management System	Universal	Farmers/ Developers	Pest Management	Crops	GitHub user	6-7	Mixed	https://github.com/18hycinthe/Smart-Agricultural-Pests-Management-System?tab=readme-over-file	Low			MIT license
Advanced Pest Detection System	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors	Pest Management	Crops	GitHub user	6-7	Mixed	https://github.com/Ali-Rizvi-1/advanced_pest_detection	Low	0	2024-08-04	GPL-3.0 license
Pest Classification and Detection System	Universal	Developers	Pest Management	Crops	https://github.com/NikhilAMathew/Pest-Classification-and-Detection-System	6-7	Edge	https://github.com/NikhilAMathew/Pest-Classification-and-Detection-System	Low	3	2025-03-08	Public Code, No license specified

								using-Deep-Learning					
BioMA (Biophysical Model Applications)	EU-focused	Developers	Pest Management	Crops	CREA - Council for Agricultural Research and Analysis of Agricultural Economics	7-8	Mixed	https://quantitative-plant.org/model/BioMA					Mentioned as open source, freeware (No license found)
Pest Detection using Deep Learning	Universal	Developers	Pest Management	Crops	GitHub user	5-6	Edge	https://github.com/shivam1423/Pest-detection	High	29	2020-12-15		Public Code, No license specified
Agricultural Pests Management	Universal	Farmers/Developers	Pest Management	Crops	GitHub user	5-6	Mixed	https://github.com/rahulkuandelwall/Aggricultural-Pests-management	Low	0	2023-10-21		Public Code, No license specified
OpeanAgri pest and disease management	Universal	Farmers/Advisors/Developers	Pest Management	Crops	OpenAgri		Mixed	https://github.com/openagri-eu/pest-and-disease-management		0	2025-04-24		EUPL-1.2 license
FluxePi	Universal	Farmers/Advisors/Developers	Irrigation	Indoor farming	Fruxefarms	7	Cloud	https://github.com/fruxefarms/FruxePi	High	41	2019-10-08		GPL 3.0 with amendments
Purdue AgIoT	Universal	Farmers/Developers/Researchers	Irrigation	Crops	Purdue University	5-6	Mixed	https://github.com/2021-Thomas/Thomas_Mayday	Low	2	2022-03-17		Public Code, No license specified
Smart AgroSensor for Irrigation Applications	Universal	Farmers/Advisors/Developers	Irrigation	Crops	GitHub user	7	Mixed	https://github.com/HaroldMurcia/smartAgroS	Low	1	2019-07-12		Public Code, No license specified

Automated Irrigation System	Universal	Farmers/Developers	Irrigation	Crops	GitHub user	5-6	Edge	https://github.com/PatrickHallek/automated-irrigation-system	Very high	95	2024-02-18	MIT license
SIP (Sustainable Irrigation Platform)	Universal	Farmers/Developers	Irrigation	Crops	GitHub user	6-7	Edge	https://github.com/Danin-CA/SIP	Very high	158	2024-12-04	GNU GPL License
OpenSprinkler	Universal	Farmers/Developers	Irrigation	Crops	OpenSprinkler	7-8	Edge	https://github.com/OpenSprinkler/OpenSprinkler-App	Very high	96	2025-04-20	GPL-3.0
Smart Irrigation Controller	Universal	Farmers/Developers	Irrigation	Crops	GitHub user	5-6	Edge	https://github.com/Gerrug/Smart-Irrigation-Controller	Low	0	2024-10-12	Public Code, No license specified
IoT-Based Smart Irrigation System	Universal	Farmers/Developers	Irrigation	Crops	GitHub user	5-6	Cloud	https://github.com/jatingrwl/IOT-Based-Smart-Irrigation-System	Low	4	2018-07-12	Public Code, No license specified
RoboRiego IoT Irrigation System	Universal	Farmers/Developers	Irrigation	Crops	GitHub user	5-6	Mixed	https://github.com/alexagonLuc16/RoboRiego-IoT-Irrigation-System	Low	0	2024-12-27	Apache-2.0 license
GardenPI	Universal	Farmers	Irrigation	Home gardens	GitHub user	5-6	Edge	https://github.com/ankitr42/gardenpi	High	9	2021-06-18	MIT license
PirriGO	Universal	Farmers/Developers	Irrigation	Crops	GitHub user	6-7	Edge	https://github.com/vacovsky/pirriGO	High	10	2024-10-19	MIT license
Moisture Monitor	Universal	Farmers/Developers	Irrigation	Crops	GitHub user	5-6	Edge	https://github.com/AbhijnanPrakash/Moisture-monitor	Low	0	2021-08-10	Public Code, No license specified
Irrigation-Pi	Universal	Farmers/Developers	Irrigation	Crops	GitHub user	6-7	Edge	https://github.com/max-	Low	3	2025-04-13	MIT license

Irrigation Controller	Universal	Farmers/ Developers	Irrigation	Crops	GitHub user	6-7	Edge	https://github.com/mwick83/irrigation-ctrl	Low	1	2021-05-01	BSD-3-Clause	
Open-Rain	Universal	Farmers	Irrigation	Crops	GitHub user	5-6	Edge	https://github.com/eloialonso/open-rain	Low	1	2022-09-20	GPL-3.0 license	
Smart Irrigation System with FC-28	Universal	Farmers/ Developers	Irrigation	Crops	GitHub user	5-6	Edge	https://github.com/deysarkarswarup/Smart-Irrigation-System	Low	0	2020-08-12	Public Code, No license specified	
IrrigationSystem	Universal	Farmers/ Developers	Irrigation	Crops	GitHub user	5-6	Edge	https://github.com/blsd1512/IrrigationSystem	Low	2	2019-04-21	Public Code, No license specified	
ESP32 Automatic Irrigation API	Universal	Farmers/ Developers	Irrigation	Crops	GitHub user	6-7	Edge	https://github.com/lsacco-B/esp32-automatic-irrigation-api	Low	0	2024-09-19	Public Code, No license specified	
IoTGreenGuardian Agriculture Automation System	Universal	Farmers/ Developers	Irrigation	Crops	GitHub user	5-6	Cloud	https://github.com/roycuadra/IoTGreenGuardian-Agriculture-Automation-System	Low	0	2023-11-30	Public Code, No license specified	
ML-Based Fog-Cloud Agricultural Irrigation System	Universal	Farmers/ Developers	Irrigation	Crops	GitHub user	5-6	Mixed	https://github.com/duanepm/ML-Based-Fog-Cloud-Agricultural-Irrigation-System	Low	0	2025-02-16	Public Code, No license specified	
Smart Irrigation System using ML and IoT	Universal	Farmers/ Developers	Irrigation	Crops	GitHub user	5-6	Cloud	https://github.com/Avdheesh616/Smart-	Low	1	2023-07-13	Public Code, No	

								Irrigation-system-using-ML-and-IoT				license specified
OpenAgri irrigation management	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Irrigation	Crops	OpenAgri		Mixed	https://github.com/openagri-irrigation-management		0	2025-04-15	EUPL-1.2 license
Livestocktracker	Universal	Farmers/ Developers	Livestock Monitoring	Livestock	GitHub user	5-6	Cloud	https://github.com/DigiBanks99/livestock-tracker	Low	5	2022-09-02	Public Code, No license specified
BovHeat	Universal	Farmers/ Researchers	Heat Stress Monitoring in Cattle	Livestock	BovHEAT	5-6	Edge	GitHub - bovheat/bovheat: Bovine Heat Detection and Analysis Tool (BovHEAT) - Automated heat detection and analysis tool for "SCR Heatime" cow activity monitoring data. https://github.com/bovheat/bovheat	Low			MIT license
Livestock Management System	Universal	Farmers/ Developers	Livestock Management	Livestock	GitHub user	5-6	Cloud	https://github.com/vikram0230/Livestock-Management-System	Low	3	2020-04-30	GPL-3.0 license
HerdNet	Universal	Farmers, Researchers	Livestock Monitoring & Tracking	Livestock	GitHub user	5-6	Edge	https://github.com/Alexandre-Delplanque/HerdNet	Low	13	2024-11-05	MIT license

LiveStock	Universal	Farmers/ Developers	Livestock Management	Livestoc k	GitHub user	5-6	Cloud	https://github.com/pedroenriquedev/LiveStock	Low	0	2023-04-30	Public Code, No license specified
Pig Weight Estimation (Pixel Occupancy Analysis)	Universal	Farmers/ Researchers	Livestock Monitoring	Livestoc k (Pigs)	GitHub user	5-6	Edge	https://github.com/nikmo/Pig-Weight-Estimation-Pixel-Occupancy-Analysis	Low	0	2023-11-27	GPL-3.0 license
KAMADHENU	Universal	Farmers/ Researchers	Livestock Monitoring & Management	Livestoc k	GitHub user	5-6	Cloud	https://github.com/MautKaFarishta/KAMADHENU	Low	0	2020-08-06	Public Code, No license specified
Demo eFarm	Universal	Farmers/ Developers	Poultry Farm Management	Poultry	GitHub user	5-6	Cloud	https://github.com/peter-evance/demo-efarm	Low	9	2024-02-22	Public Code, No license specified
Poultry Farming Management System	Universal	Farmers/ Developers	Poultry Farm Management	Poultry	GitHub user	5-6	Cloud	https://github.com/Musanza/Poultry-farming-management-system	Low	19	2022-02-26	Public Code, No license specified
Sen4Cap	Czech Republic/Italy/Lithuania/Netherlands/Romania/Spanish region Castilla y Leon	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Farm management/ Agricultural practices monitoring	Crops	DG-Agri/DG-Grow/DG-JRC	7	Cloud	https://github.com/Sen4CAP/Sen4CAP/tree/master/licenses	High	6	2023-03-24	https://github.com/Sen4CAP/Sen4CAP/tree/master/licenses
farmOS	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers/ Researchers	Farm management	Crops	farmOS	7	Cloud	https://github.com/farmOS/farmOS	Very high	298	2025-04-24	GPL-2.0 license

FarmMaps (Akkerweb). Open Source based/ Public code	Netherlands	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Farm management	Crops	AKKERWEB FOUNDATI ON	7	Cloud	https://git.akerweb.nl/explore/repos	-				Various License Open-Source based/Open code
Crop Planning Software	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Farm management	Crops	GitHub user	4	Cloud	https://github.com/claytonrcarter/cropplanning	High	33	2019-05-02	GPL-3.0 license	
FarmBot OS Web app	Universal	Farmers/ Developers	Small Farms/Gardens management	Crops	FarmBot	7	Cloud	https://github.com/FarmBot/Farmbot-Web-App	Very high	346	2025-04-18	MIT license	
Litefarm	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Farm management	Crops	LiteFarmOrg	7	Cloud	https://github.com/LiteFarmOrg/LiteFarm	High	86	2025-04-24	GPL-3.0 license	
AgStack Asset Registry 1.0/2.0	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Farm management	Crops	Linux Foundation	5	Cloud	https://github.com/agstack/asset-registry	High	4	2025-04-07	Public Code, No license specified	
Agstack Weather Server	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Farm management	Crops	Linux Foundation	5	Cloud	https://github.com/agstack/weather-server	High	3	2021-12-16	Apache-2.0 license	
Agstack Ag-rec	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Farm management	Crops	Linux Foundation	5	Cloud	https://github.com/agstack/ag-rec	High	4	2022-01-08	Apache-2.0 license	
Ekylibre	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Farm management	Crops	Ekylibre	7	Cloud	https://github.com/ekylibre/ekylibre	High	164	2024-02-22	AGPL-3.0 license	
Tania	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Farm management	Crops	Tania	7	Cloud	https://github.com/usetania/tania-core	Very high	163	2024-06-13	Apache-2.0 license	
Agrosense	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Farm management	Crops	GitHub user	7	Mixed	https://github.com/HaroldMurcia/AgroSenseV1.0	Low	2	2021-04-30	Public Code, No license specified	

Farm Data Relay System	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Broadband Connectivity	ALL	GitHub user	7	Cloud	https://github.com/timmbogner/Farm-Data-Relay-System	Very high	123	2025-04-01	MIT license
Open Food Network	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Distribution	ALL	Open Food Foundation	7	Cloud	https://github.com/openfoodfoundation/openfoodnetwork	Very high	733	2025-04-24	AGPL-3.0 license
QuantiFarm Benchmarking of farming practices tool	Universal	Developers/ Advisors	Digital recording of farming practices and benchmarking on the use of inputs	Crops	QuantiFarm project	6	Mixed	https://gitlab.com/QuantiFarm/benchmarking-tool	Low			Public Code, No license specified
OpeanAgri Farm Calendar	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Farm management	Crops/Li vestock	OpenAgri		Mixed	https://github.com/openagri-eu/farmcalendar		0	2025-04-24	EUPL-1.2 license
OpeanAgri weather- service	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Farm management	Crops/Li vestock	OpenAgri		Mixed	https://github.com/openagri-eu/weather-service		0	2025-04-22	EUPL-1.2 license
OpenAgri reporting service	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Farm management	Crops/Li vestock	OpenAgri		Mixed	https://github.com/openagri-eu/reporting-service		0	2025-04-07	EUPL-1.2 license

Table 3: Open Source Software Agricultural Digital Solutions Simpler Components: Farm management tools

ADS	COUNTRY (information of current pilots/ mostly universal replicability)	END-USER	AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION STEP	CROP/LI VESTOCK	ORGANIZATION	TRL	EDGE/CL OUD/MIX ED	URL	Communi ty Engage ment	Numbe r of forks	Last commi t	Licens e
FarmVibes.Connect	Countries where unused TV spectrum is legal to use	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Broadband Connectivity	Crops	Microsoft	7	Mixed	https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/research/project/project-farmvibes/articles/farmvibes-connect/				Not yet available on github / No license specified
FarmVibes.Edge	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Edge data-processing connected to drones	Crops	Microsoft	7	Edge	https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/research/project/project-farmvibes/articles/farmvibes-edge/				Not yet available on github / No license specified
FarmVibes.Bot	Universal/in use in subharan Africa	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Farm management/Commu nication	Crops	Microsoft	7	Cloud	https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/research/project/project-farmvibes/articles/farmvibes-bot/				Not yet available on github / No license specified
FarmVibes.AI	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Farm management	Crops	Microsoft	7	Cloud	https://github.com/microsoft/farmvibes-ai		138	2024-11-29	MIT license
Open Ag component: OpenATK Tillage App	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Farm management	Crops	OpenATK	5	Cloud	https://github.com/OpenATK/Tillage		2	2013-12-12	Public Code, No license specified

Open Ag component: OpenATK Rock App	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Farm management	Crops	OpenATK	5	Cloud	https://github.com/OpenATK/TheRockApp		4	2018-11-27	Public Code, No license specified
Open Ag component: OpenATK Soil mapping	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Farm management	Crops	OpenATK	5	Cloud	https://github.com/OpenATK/soils-mapping	Low	1	2022-07-18	Public Code, No license specified
Open Ag component: OpenATK Field Work App	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Farm management	Crops	OpenATK	5	Cloud	https://github.com/OpenATK/FieldWorkApp	Low	1	2021-04-18	Public Code, No license specified
Open Ag component: OpenATK Field Manure App	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Farm management	Livestock	OpenATK	5	Cloud	https://github.com/OpenATK/ManureApp	Low	2	2018-05-01	Public Code, No license specified
Open Ag component: OpenATK Harvest progress viewer	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Farm management	Crops	OpenATK	5	Cloud	https://github.com/OpenATK/HarvestProgressViewer	Low	1	2020-12-08	Public Code, No license specified
GDAY model	Universal	Developers/ Researchers	Fertilization	Crops	GitHub user	3	Cloud	https://github.com/mdekauwe/GDAY	Low	31	2021-10-18	Public Code, No license specified
Farmtopia data exchange module	Universal	Developers	Agricultural data sharing	ALL	Farmtopia project	6	Cloud	https://github.com/Farmtopia/data-exchange	Low			Public Code, No license specified
Farmtopia digital field book	Universal	Developers	Digital recording of farming practices	ALL	Farmtopia project	6	Cloud	https://github.com/Farmtopia/digital-field-book	Low			Public Code, No license

												specified
Soilmate	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Fertilization/ Irrigation	Crops	Open-Source-Agriculture/soil_logr	7	Cloud	https://github.com/Open-Source-Agriculture/soil_logr	Low	0	2021-03-22	GPL-3.0 license
AgML	Universal	Developers	ALL	ALL	Project-AgML	7	Cloud	https://github.com/Project-AgML/AgML	High	32	2025-04-22	Apache-2.0 license
OpenFarm	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Farming & Gardening knowledge	Crops/PI ants	openfarmcc	7	Cloud	https://github.com/openfarmcc/OpenFarm	Very high	247	2025-04-22	MIT license
Crop yield Prediction	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Farm management	Crops	GitHub user	5	Cloud	https://github.com/JiaxuanYou/crop_yield_prediction	Very high	208	2021-03-01	Public Code, No license specified
Dro-Matic	Universal	Farmers/ Advisors/ Developers	Fertilization/ Irrigation/ Pest management	Crops	GitHub user	5	Edge	https://github.com/drolsen/DRO-Matic	Very high	93	2018-01-26	Public Code, No license specified
AgIsoStack++	Universal	Developers/ Farmers	Interoperability	Crops	Open-Agriculture	5	Edge	https://github.com/Open-Agriculture/AgIsoStack-plus-plus	High	57	2025-04-17	MIT license
AgIsoStack-Arduino	Universal	Developers/ Farmers	Interoperability	Crops	Open-Agriculture	5	Edge	https://github.com/Open-Agriculture/AgIsoStack-Arduino	Low	3	2024-10-20	MIT license
ADAPT toolkit	Universal	Developers/ Farmers	Interoperability	Crops	Ag Gateway	7	Edge	https://github.com/ADAPT	High			EPL-1.0 license
Fields2Cover	Universal	Developers/ Farmers	Automation in Agriculture	Crops	Fields2Cover	7	Edge	https://github.com/Fields2Cover/Fields2Cover	Very high	123	2025-04-22	BSD 3-Clause License

AgOpenGPS	Universal	Developers	Farm management/ Map service	ALL	AgOpenGPS-Official	7	Cloud	https://github.com/AgOpenGPS-Official/AgOpenGPS	Very high	280	2025-04-23	GNU GENERAL PUBLIC LICENSE
Agroclimatology	Universal	Developers	Climate data service	Crops	GitHub user	5	Cloud	https://github.com/brycejohnston/agroclimatology	Low	3	2017-08-30	MIT license
Evapotranspiration	Universal	Developers	Climate data service	Crops	GitHub user	5	Cloud	https://github.com/brycejohnston/evapotranspiration	Low	3	2017-08-30	BSD 3-Clause License
Cotton Phenology Dataset	Greece	Developers/ Researchers	Farm Management (Crop Phenology Monitoring)	Cotton	Agri-Hub	6	Cloud	https://github.com/Agri-Hub/cotton-phenology-dataset	Low	9	2023-03-09	Public Code, No license specified
OpenAgri CSM	Universal	Developers	Farm management	ALL	OpenAgri		Mixed	https://github.com/openagri-eu/OCSM		0	2025-03-31	EUPL-1.2 license
OpenAgri Gatekeeper	Universal	Developers	Farm management	ALL	OpenAgri		Mixed	https://github.com/openagri-eu/Gatekeeper		0	2025-04-22	EUPL-1.2 license

Table 4: Open Source Software Agricultural Digital Solutions Simpler Components: IoT Integration & Data Processing and Analytics

ADS	COUNTRY (information of current pilots/ mostly universal replicability)	END-USER	AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION STEP	CROP/ LIVESTOCK	ORGANIZATION	TRL	EDGE/CL OUD/MIX ED	URL	Community Engagement	Number of forks	Last commit	License
Fiware - Wilma	Universal	Developers	IOT integration	ALL	FIWARE Foundation	6	Cloud	https://github.com/FIWARE-GEs/wilma	High	0	2023-08-31	MIT license
Fiware - Cosmos	Universal	Developers	IOT integration	ALL	FIWARE Foundation	6	Cloud	https://github.com/telefonicaid/fiware-cosmos?tab=AGPL-3.0-1-ov-1-ov-file#readme	High			AGPL-3.0 license
Fiware - Backend Device Management - IDAS	Universal	Developers	IOT integration	ALL	FIWARE Foundation	6	Cloud	https://github.com/FIWARE/catalogue/blob/master/iot-agents/README.md	High	40	2025-04-21	AGPL-3.0 license
Fiware - ORION	Universal	Developers	IOT integration	ALL	FIWARE Foundation	6	Cloud	https://github.com/telefonicaid/fiware-orion	High	265	2025-04-24	AGPL-3.0 license
Fiware - Keyrock	Universal	Developers	IOT integration	ALL	FIWARE Foundation	6	Cloud	https://github.com/gingfiware-idm	High	81	2023-11-28	MIT license
InfluxDB	Universal	Developers	Data Processing and Analytics	ALL	InfluxData	7	Mixed	https://github.com/influxdata/influxdb	Very high	3600	2025-04-25	Apache-2.0, MIT
Note-Red	Universal	Developers	IOT integration	ALL	node-red	7	Mixed	https://github.com/node-red/node-red	Very high	3538	2025-04-14	MIT license
Grafana	Universal	Developers	Data Processing and Analytics	ALL	Grafana labs	7	Cloud	https://github.com/grafana/grafana	Very high	12563	2025-04-25	AGPL-3.0 license

MongoDB	Universal	Developers	Data Processing and Analytics	ALL	MongoDB	7	Cloud	https://github.com/mongodb/mongo	Very high	5649	2025-04-25	https://github.com/mongodb/mongo?tab=license-1-over-file#readme
Zenoh	Universal	Developers	IOT integration	ALL	eclipse-zenoh	7	Cloud	https://github.com/eclipse-zenoh/zenoh	Very high	187	2025-04-24	https://github.com/eclipse-zenoh/zenoh?tab=license-1-over-file#readme
Mosquitto	Universal	Developers	IOT integration	ALL	Eclipse Mosquitto	7	Hybrid	https://github.com/eclipse-mosquitto/mosquitto	Very high	2500	2025-04-24	Eclipse Public License 2.0 and the Eclipse Distribution License 1.0
Contiki	Universal	Developers	IOT integration	ALL	Contiki-os	7	Edge	https://github.com/contiki-os/contiki	Very high	2600	2018-11-13	3-clause BSD license
FreeRTOS	Universal	Developers	IOT integration	ALL	FreeRTOS	7	Edge	https://github.com/FreeRTOS/FreeRTOS	Very high	1700	2025-04-24	MIT license
Minio	Universal	Developers	Data Processing and Analytics	ALL	MinIO	7	Hybrid	https://github.com/minio/minio	Very high	5800	2025-04-24	AGPL-3.0 license

Streamlit	Universal	Developers	Data Processing and Analytics	ALL	Streamlit	7	Hybrid	https://github.com/streamlit/streamlit	Very high	3400	2025-04-24	Apache-2.0 license
Postgres	Universal	Developers	Data Processing and Analytics	ALL	PostgreSQL	7	Hybrid	https://github.com/postgres/postgres	Very high	4900	2025-04-24	License
Ryax- engine	Universal	Developers	Data Processing and Analytics	ALL	Ryax technologies	5	Cloud	https://github.com/RyaxTech/ryax-engine?tab=readme-ov-file	High			MPL-2.0 license
ThingsBoard - Open-source IoT Platform	Universal	Developers	IOT integration	ALL	ThingsBoard	9	Cloud	https://github.com/thingsboard/thingsboard	Very high	5506	2025-04-24	Apache v2.0
Prometheus	Universal	Developers	Data Processing and Analytics	ALL	Prometheus	9	Cloud	https://github.com/prometheus/prometheus	Very high	9530	2025-04-25	Apache-2.0 license
Senslog	Universal	Developers	IOT integration	ALL	GitHub user	6	Cloud	https://github.com/mkepk/senslog	Low	1	2019-08-15	BSD 3-Clause License
DJI Payload SDK	Universal	Developers	IOT integration	ALL	dji-sdk	9	Edge	https://github.com/dji-sdk/Payload-SDK	Very high	141	2025-04-18	MIT License
EdgeX Foundry	Universal	Developers	IOT integration	ALL	Linux Foundation	5	Cloud	https://github.com/edgexfoundry/	Very high			Apache-2.0 license
eKuiper	Universal	Developers	IOT integration	ALL	Linux Foundation	5	Cloud	https://github.com/lf-edge/ekuiper	Very high	425	2025-04-24	Apache-2.0 license
NanoMQ	Universal	Developers	IOT integration	ALL	Linux Foundation	5	Cloud	https://github.com/nanomq/nanomq	Very high	222	2025-04-15	MIT license
QGIS	Universal	Developers	Map service	ALL	QGIS Development Team	9	Cloud	https://qgis.org/nl/site/	Very high			GNU GENERAL PUBLIC LICENSE

HSlayers NG	Universal	Developers	Map service	Crops	hslayers	4	Cloud	https://github.com/hslayers/hslayers-ng	Low	20	2025-04-22	MIT license
(Open)Micka	Universal	Developers	Map service	Crops	hsrcz	4	Cloud	https://github.com/hsrcz/Micka	Low	6	2024-10-29	BSD-3-Clause license
Geoserver	Universal	Developers	Map service	ALL	geoserver	9	Cloud	https://github.com/geoserver/geoserver	Very high	2214	2025-04-24	GNU General Public License Version 2.0 license
Rastervision	Universal	Developers	Map service	Crops	azavea	7	Cloud	https://github.com/azavea/rastervision	Very high	391	2025-04-04	Apache 2 license
GSODR	Universal	Developers	Climate data service	Crops	ropensci	5	Cloud	https://github.com/ropensci/GSODR	High	17	2025-03-06	MIT license
Open Meteo	Universal	Developers	Climate data service	ALL	open-meteo	9	Cloud	https://github.com/open-meteo/open-meteo	Very high	210	2025-04-23	AGPL-3.0 license
WeeWX- Open source software for your weather station	Universal	Developers	Climate data service	ALL	weewx	9	Cloud	https://github.com/weewx/weewx	Very high	311	2025-03-27	GPL-3.0 license

Table 5: Open Hardware-based Agricultural Digital Solutions

ADS	COUNTRY (current prototypes/ universal replicability)	END-USER	AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION STEP	CROP/ LIVESTOCK	ORGANIZATION	TRL	EDGE/CL OUD/MIXED	URL	Community Engagement	Number of forks	Last commit	License
Fido, the temperature alarm that sends text messages	USA	Farmers	Greenhouse Temperature/data	Greenhouse	openpipekit	4-5	Edge	https://github.com/openpipekit/fido	Low	3	2020-07-30	Public Code, No license specified
Seeder Roller Generator for Jang seeders	USA	Farmers	Sowing	ALL	Makeshop	5	Edge	https://github.com/Makeshop/SeederRollerGenerator	Low	3	2016-02-23	Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported (CC-by-S.A.)
Rover - Remote Electric Fence Switch by Text Message	USA	Farmers	Farm management	ALL	Farmhack user	6	Edge	https://farmhack.org/tools/rover-remote-electric-fence-switch-text-message				CC-BY-4.0
Temperature Data Logger	USA	Farmers	Farm management	ALL	Farmhack user	6	Edge	https://farmhack.org/tools/temperature-data-logger				CC-BY-4.0
Orchard bird scare machines	USA	Fruit growers	Farm management	Fruits	Farmhack user	6	Edge	https://farmhack.org/tools/orchard-bird-scare-machines				CC-BY-4.0
FarmBot	USA	Farmers	Small Farms/Gardens management	ALL	FarmBot	9	Mixed	https://github.com/Farm	High	17	2024-09-11	Licenses

Electronic Flame Weeder System	USA	Farmers	Mowing	ALL	Farmhack User	4	Edge	rotational-grazing-0 https://farmhack.org/tools/electronic-flame-weeder-system					CC-BY-4.0
Anavi Gardening UHAT	Bulgaria	Farmers	monitoring and growing plants	Plants	AnaviTechnology	6	Edge	https://github.com/AnaviTechnology/anavi-docs/tree/main/anavi-gardening-uhat	High	36	2025-04-25	CC-BY-4.0	
Baby groot	Mexico	Farmers	Irrigation	Crops	GitHub user	6	Edge	https://github.com/Sxyther/BabyGroot v1-1/	Low	1	2019-03-24	Software License: GPL v3. Hardware License: CERN Hardware released under an Open Hardware License v1.2.	
Customized Automated Resource Regulation and Optimization Technology	Canada	Farmers	Irrigation	Crops	GitHub user	4-5	Edge	https://github.com/Artemis5010/C.A.R.R.O.T./tree/main	Low	1	2024-05-21	CC-BY-4.0	
Parametric cold-frame agrivoltaic systems	Canada	Farmers/Advisors	gardening in cold climates	Crops	Joshua Pierce	6	Edge	https://osf.io/k6xwv/				GNU General Public	

														Licence (GPL) 3.0
IOT agointelligence lorawan node	Portugal	Farmers/ Developers	Farm management	ALL	GitHub user	6	Edge	https://github.com/antoniovalente/IoT-AgroIntelligence-Node	Low	2	2020-11-16	CERN Open Hardware License Version 2 - Permissive		
Vinduino soil moisture sensor station	USA	Farmers/ Developers	Irrigation	Crops	GitHub user	7	Edge	https://github.com/ReinerVindul/Vinduino	High	55	2021-03-11	GPL-3.0 license		
Colubris LoRa Meteorological Station Board	Brazil	Farmers/ Developers	Weather data service	ALL	embarcaco.es	5-6	Edge	https://github.com/embarcacoes/estacao-metereologica-lorawan/				CERN Open Hardware License Version 2		
Green Detect	Italy	Farmers/ Developers	Environmental monitoring	ALL	GitHub user	5-6	Edge	https://github.com/GreenDets/bms/GreenDetect	Low	2	2022-07-12	CC-BY-4.0		
Iguana	Chile	Farmers/ Developers	Irrigation/ Soil Moisture	ALL	iowlabs	7	Edge	https://github.com/iowlabs/iguana	Low	0	2024-01-31	Licenses		
OpenScout	UK	Farmers/ Developers	Farm management	Crops	GitHub user	7	Edge	https://github.com/cbedio/OpenScout	High	12	2025-01-28	GPL-3.0 license		
Phecda	Chile	Farmers/ Developers	Fertilization	Crops	iowlabs	6	Edge	https://github.com/iowlabs/peheda	Low	0	2024-03-12	Licenses		
Twig	USA	Farmers/ Developers	Irrigation/ Soil Moisture	Crops	juniper-garden	6	Edge	https://github.com/juniper-garden/twig_temp_humidity_sensor	Low	3	2023-05-17	GPL-3.0 license		

Mobile Hop Picker	USA	Farmers	Harvesting	Crops	Farmhack User	7	Edge	https://farmhack.org/tools/mobile-mechanized-hops-harvester					CC-BY-4.0
l'Otomate	Canada	Farmers	Greenhouse management	Greenhouse	LoupeHC	7	Edge	https://github.com/LoupeHC/controlleur-CAPE	Low	4	2019-02-17	LGPL-3.0 license	
Weedinator	UK	Farmers/Developers	Weed Control	Crops	Goat Industries	7	Edge	https://hackaday.io/project/53896-weedinator-2019				Software: GPLv3; Hardware: Creative Commons BY-SA	
Irrigation Controller	Universal	Farmers/Developers	Irrigation	Crops	GitHub user	6-7	Edge	https://github.com/mwikk83/irrigation_ctrl_hw		1	2018-01-24	BSD 3-clause	
BeagleV Ahead	USA	Farmers/Developers	IoT integration	ALL	beaglev-ahead	6-7	Edge	https://git.beagleboard.org/beaglev-ahead/beaglev-ahead				CC-BY-4.0	
BG0249_DepthAI_RGB_Camera	USA	Farmers/Developers	IoT integration	ALL	luxonis	6-7	Edge	https://github.com/luxonis/depthai-hardware/tree/master/BG0249_DepthAI_RGB_Camera		121	2024-12-19	MIT	
Open Weather Station	Universal	Farmers/Developers	Climate data service	ALL	GitHub user	6-7	Edge	https://github.com/panchazo/open-weather-station	High	17	2024-11-21	Apache 2 license	
HidroIoT	Guatemala	Farmers/Developers	Irrigation	Crops	GitHub user	4-5	Edge	https://github.com/AlisonRequena/Hidro_IOT?ta	Low			Hardware: CERN-OHL-P-	

								b=readme-ov-file					2 Software: GPL-3
Nordic sdk	Universal	Farmers/ Developers	IoT integration	ALL	nrfconnect	8-9	Mixed	https://github.com/nrfconnect/sdk-nrf	Very high	1303	2025-04-25		LicenseRef-Nordic-5-Clause
Hyphascope	Japan	Farmers/ Developers/ Researchers	Pest management/ Fertilization	Crops	GitHub user	5-6	Edge	https://github.com/h-schaefer/hyphascope	Low	0	2025-03-17		MIT
Rootmaster	Sweden	Farmers/ Developers	Fertilization/ Irrigation	Crops	openhydroponics	6-7	Edge	https://github.com/openhydroponics/hw/rootmaster					CERN-OHL-W-2.0

3.1.1. Geographic and contextual replicability

An important dimension of assessing Agricultural Digital Solutions (ADSs) is their geographic or contextual replicability—that is, the extent to which a solution has been validated or deployed in a particular region or under specific agro-climatic and socio-economic conditions. In this updated catalogue, we aimed to expand and refine the available data on regional applicability. However, the overall availability of such information remains limited. Most open-source ADSs currently included in the catalogue present universal or undefined replicability. This is due either to their design as general-purpose tools (especially in the case of farm management platforms and IoT components) or to the lack of regional metadata in their public repositories. For many tools, there is no clear information about where they have been tested, implemented, or optimized. As a result, their replicability must be considered theoretically broad, but not verifiably validated in specific conditions. Some differentiation exists in farm management tools, where we can infer applicability based on the scale and scope of use. Several tools appear tailored for smaller-scale operations (e.g. Tania, LiteFarm, farmOS), while others, especially those associated with European public institutions or larger networks, may scale more effectively to larger or multi-farm settings (e.g. Sen4Cap, FaST). However, for solutions targeting specific agricultural production steps, such as pest management, fertilization, or irrigation, geographic replicability is often under-documented. In many cases, even for AI-based models or sensor-driven systems, the training datasets, environmental assumptions, or target crops and regions are not clearly defined. This represents a critical shortcoming in many open-source ADSs: the absence of accompanying documentation and evidence that would describe the development context, region of use, or data sources. While a few exceptions exist, such as solutions from EU-funded projects, this is not the norm.

This limitation has a direct implication for the Decision Support Tool (DST). The DST will perform geographic similarity assessments (based on environmental, socio-economic, and connectivity indicators) to recommend solutions. However, this functionality can only be fully applied to solutions for which regional origin, deployment, or validation is known. For many catalogue entries, this information is simply unavailable, limiting the precision of location-based recommendations. We anticipate this issue will gradually be addressed as more regionally grounded solutions are added—particularly those developed within the OpenAgri Sustainable Innovation Pilots, which are expected to provide well-documented deployment contexts. In future iterations of the catalogue, we will also continue to monitor and document any new information or publications that may emerge for existing tools, especially those for which deployment data is not yet publicly shared. Overall, this section highlights a broader structural gap in open-source ADS development: while transparency in code and architecture is a hallmark, transparency in deployment context, regional performance, and data provenance remains lacking in many cases. Identifying this as a priority for improvement will help guide future updates and engagement with developers.

3.1.2. Technology Readiness Level

The Technology Readiness Level (TRL) remains a key indicator in assessing the maturity and deployment readiness of the Agricultural Digital Solutions (ADSs) included in this catalogue. In this updated iteration, TRL values were assigned to all newly documented solutions and re-evaluated for existing entries to ensure greater accuracy and alignment with current developments. The TRL values in this catalogue are estimates, informed by publicly available documentation, repository activity, deployment history, and—when necessary—expert judgment. As few projects explicitly state their TRL, this method allows for a consistent comparative basis across a wide range of solutions. The standard 1–9 TRL scale was applied, where TRL 4–6 represents technologies in active development or validation stages, and TRL 7–9 refers to mature, widely deployed systems. Across the catalogue, the majority of complete open-source software solutions fall within

the TRL 6–8 range. These include robust tools like *farmOS*, *Sen4Cap*, and *Harvestify*, which are actively used and well-documented. Simpler software components—used for IoT integration, data analytics, or farm connectivity—also generally fall in the mid to high TRL range, often between TRL 6 and 7, reflecting their operational readiness and frequent use in broader digital agriculture systems. Examples include *InfluxDB*, *Grafana*, *Node-Red*, and *Fiware ORION*. The open hardware-based solutions display greater variability. While some, like *FarmBot Genesis* or *Weedinator*, are closer to TRL 7–9 and have documented field deployments, others remain in TRL 4–6, reflecting prototype-level implementations, community-led experimentation, or limited regional use. This diversity underscores both the innovative potential and the still-developing nature of many open hardware tools. By reassessing the TRL of previously catalogued solutions and evaluating new entries, this iteration provides a more reliable snapshot of technological maturity. This information is especially critical for the upcoming Decision Support Tool (DST), where TRL will help filter and prioritize solutions according to their deployment readiness.

3.1.3. End-User Type

The updated catalogue of Agricultural Digital Solutions (ADSs) continues to serve a broad spectrum of end-users, reinforcing the inclusive and flexible nature of open-source technologies in agriculture. As in the first iteration, the primary end-user groups remain farmers, advisors, developers, and researchers. However, this second version places greater emphasis on the evolving dynamics between these roles, particularly as the catalogue becomes more tightly integrated with the Decision Support Tool (DST). Farmers remain the central target group for most complete solutions. These tools support decision-making and automation in core agricultural production steps such as fertilization, irrigation, pest management, and livestock monitoring. Several new entries in the catalogue are specifically tailored to their direct use—for instance, *OpenWeedLocator* for weed detection and *BovHeat* for monitoring heat stress in cattle. Advisors, including agronomists and consultants, benefit from tools that offer regional and farm-level insights, enabling more personalized support to their clients. Solutions such as *Sen4Cap* and *LiteFarm* provide multi-farm monitoring features and interfaces designed to support advisory workflows. Developers are increasingly prominent end-users in this iteration. The catalogue now includes a greater number of simpler components—IoT integration modules, map services, analytics tools, and data models—that can be combined to build or customize ADSs. Examples such as *Node-RED*, *Zenoh*, and *Fiware ORION* are highly relevant in this context. Developers are also empowered to create tailored solutions for specific biogeographic contexts, which is particularly relevant for the developer-facing DST module. Researchers use many of the same tools as developers but typically focus on experimentation, data modeling, and validation. The inclusion of more open-source models (e.g., *Agstack Pest Models* or *BioMA*) and datasets (e.g., *Cotton Phenology Dataset*) reflects their growing role in generating, testing, and refining agricultural innovations. Many ADSs are explicitly multi-user, designed to support collaboration between different actors. A tool like *farmOS*, for example, is equally applicable to farmers for operational management, advisors for performance tracking, developers for module extension, and researchers for data-driven experimentation. This versatility is a defining feature of many open-source solutions and a critical asset in fostering integrated agricultural innovation. This updated end-user analysis not only strengthens the catalogue’s utility for various stakeholders but also supports the logic of the DST. Each module of the DST is built around these user categories, and the catalogue’s alignment with their distinct and overlapping needs enhances its relevance and practical applicability.

3.1.4. Targeted Agricultural Production Step

This updated catalogue continues to classify ADSs according to the specific agricultural production steps they support. These steps remain central to the logic of the catalogue structure and to the intended functionality of the DST, which relies on this classification to guide users toward the most relevant technologies for their operational needs. Farm management remains one of the most prominent focus areas. Several established

platforms, such as farmOS, LiteFarm, and Tania, provide integrated functionalities for managing crops, livestock, tasks, and resources. These universal platforms are complemented by newer modular tools, including solutions developed within the OpenAgri project like the farm calendar and reporting services, offering more flexible and context-specific options for users seeking to implement or expand digital recordkeeping and farm planning.

Building on the initial version of the catalogue, this iteration has notably expanded its coverage of solutions for specific agricultural production steps such as pest management, irrigation, fertilization, and livestock management. These areas were prioritized in response to the co-creation process around the DST, which highlighted the need for more complete and directly deployable tools across these key domains. Pest management is now addressed by a broader array of AI-based tools and detection models. These include deep learning models for pest identification, edge-based monitoring systems, and hybrid solutions that combine field-level detection with cloud-based analytics. Similarly, the irrigation category now includes a wide range of tools with varying degrees of automation and connectivity requirements, from entirely offline systems designed for smallholder settings to cloud-integrated platforms capable of real-time data processing and predictive irrigation control. The fertilization category has also been strengthened with additional digital solutions that leverage AI, environmental data, and cloud platforms to optimize nutrient management. These range from full-scale decision support systems to more focused tools designed for edge deployment. Livestock management and monitoring has seen particular improvement, with tools now covering tasks such as animal tracking, heat stress detection, weight estimation, and general farm operations management for both large-scale and smaller livestock farms. While these production-step-specific solutions are central, the catalogue also continues to document simpler components and services that support them indirectly. These include weather data services, geospatial mapping platforms, IoT integration tools, and data analytics frameworks, which can be combined with the main solutions to build more tailored and sophisticated agricultural systems.

3.1.5. Scale of Supportive Community & repositories metrics

This updated iteration expands the evaluation of community engagement for both open-source software and open hardware-based Agricultural Digital Solutions (ADSs), introducing a more nuanced set of repository metrics to assess the activity and vitality of the ecosystems surrounding these tools. As in the first iteration, GitHub stars are used as a basic indicator of overall interest and community visibility. The classification system remains the same: solutions with fewer than 50 stars are considered to have low community support, those with 50–200 stars as high, and those with more than 200 stars as very high. However, this iteration also includes two additional metrics—number of forks and date of last commit—retrieved via GitHub API on 24 April 2025. These provide important context for understanding the development dynamics behind each solution. The number of forks indicates the extent to which other developers have cloned or built upon a project, often reflecting experimentation, modification, or integration into broader toolchains. Meanwhile, the date of the last commit reveals how actively a solution is being maintained or updated—an important proxy for its long-term reliability and relevance. Together, these metrics offer a fuller picture of the ongoing technical activity and the responsiveness of the development community. For open-source software solutions, especially those in categories such as IoT integration, data analytics, and farm management platforms, community engagement tends to be higher. Many of these tools serve multiple domains beyond agriculture—ranging from environmental monitoring to industrial systems—resulting in larger and more active communities. In particular, high-profile components like Grafana, InfluxDB, or Node-RED are supported by robust developer ecosystems and frequent releases, ensuring continued improvements and strong interoperability. For open hardware-based ADSs, community metrics are less consistently available, due to the decentralized and often informal nature of hardware documentation and development. While some projects do maintain GitHub repositories or use platforms like FarmHack or GitLab, many offer

documentation through independent websites or forums, which do not provide structured engagement data. Where GitHub repositories are available, the same metrics (stars, forks, and last commits) have been applied, although values tend to be lower on average. This does not necessarily reflect lower utility but often stems from the more specialized or regional nature of hardware projects, as well as differences in how hardware is developed and shared. Overall, this updated analysis highlights a key insight: the strength of an open-source ADS is not only in its technical functionality but also in the depth and responsiveness of its development community. These new metrics help stakeholders better gauge the maturity and sustainability of each solution when considering adoption, integration, or further development.

3.1.6. Connectivity Requirements and Dependencies

In this second iteration of the catalogue, the classification of Open Source Agricultural Digital Solutions (ADSs) has been significantly refined to better reflect their operational connectivity needs. While the first iteration primarily grouped solutions under the broader categories of edge, cloud, or mixed-model deployment, this version introduces a new qualitative variable—Connectivity Requirements/Dependencies—designed to give a more practical and nuanced understanding of how each solution functions in relation to internet access. This added field was developed after a systematic analysis of the solutions' repositories, documentation, and where available, code-level infrastructure details. The goal was to better inform the Decision Support Tool (DST), which incorporates regional connectivity indexes when recommending appropriate digital tools. The new categorization breaks down connectivity requirements into four levels: none, minimal, medium, and maximum. These levels reflect both the dependency of the solution on internet access and the nature of its deployment model. Solutions labeled as “none” are fully operational offline and require no internet connectivity. These are typically edge-based systems that perform local processing on-device. For example, Automated Irrigation System, SIP (Sustainable Irrigation Platform), and Eco-fertilization can operate independently in the field without ever connecting to the cloud. Similarly, some pest detection systems, such as Insect Detection on Sticky Traps and Pest Detection using Deep Learning, run deep learning models entirely on local devices, enabling their use in low-connectivity or disconnected environments. Solutions marked as “minimal” operate mostly offline but include optional cloud-based features. These tools might benefit from occasional connectivity to sync data, perform updates, or upload reports. For instance, OpenAgri Reporting Service works offline but can upload reports to the cloud when internet access is available. OpenATK Field Work App and FarmVibes.Edge also fall in this category, where core features are locally available, but full functionality is unlocked with periodic internet access. In hardware, examples such as Iguana and Twig represent tools that monitor soil moisture on-device while offering optional cloud sync for remote monitoring. Solutions classified under “medium” operate under hybrid models, with key components functioning on the edge but requiring intermittent cloud access for analytics, data storage, or model updates. For example, the Smart Agricultural Pest Management System processes pest-related data locally but uploads results to the cloud for visualization. Similarly, irrigation systems like RoboRiego IoT or IoTGreenGuardian are designed to function locally but depend on cloud platforms for monitoring and adjustments. On the open hardware side, Compost Sensor and Grower Bot illustrate this middle ground, operating independently while benefiting from periodic cloud integration. Solutions labeled “maximum” have full dependency on internet connectivity. These are typically cloud-native platforms that either stream data continuously or rely entirely on web-based dashboards and processing. Farm management tools such as farmOS, Litefarm, FaST, and Sen4Cap fall into this category, as do many AI-powered tools such as FarmVibes.AI and data-sharing platforms like Farmland Data Exchange. These solutions are highly scalable and computationally powerful, but without reliable internet connectivity, their core functions cannot be accessed. Similarly, cloud services used for climate and weather data like Open Meteo, GSODR, and WeeWX

also fall under this maximum dependency category. This more detailed assessment allows stakeholders to better evaluate which tools are realistically deployable under different technological constraints. For example, in regions identified through the DST as having poor rural connectivity, solutions in the “none” or “minimal” categories would be prioritized. Conversely, areas with robust internet infrastructure can benefit from the advanced features of high-dependency, cloud-native platforms. It’s important to note that these classifications were made based on publicly available information in the repositories. In many cases, the lack of clear architectural documentation or user manuals made it necessary to infer connectivity needs based on deployment models, code structure, and stated system requirements. As such, these designations are best understood as informed estimates that will be refined in future iterations of the catalogue. This deeper understanding of connectivity dependencies complements the edge/cloud/mixed classification and is critical for operationalizing the DST. By aligning digital solutions with on-the-ground infrastructure realities, this deliverable takes a major step toward ensuring that selected ADSs are not only functionally appropriate but also practically deployable.

3.1.7. Organizations, Licenses and repository availability

A critical focus in the second iteration of the catalogue was a deeper examination of the organizational ownership, licensing status, and repository availability of the documented Agricultural Digital Solutions (ADSs). This effort was essential not only for improving the transparency and usability of the catalogue but also for helping end-users navigate the legal and practical frameworks associated with open-source technologies. For each solution, the organization or individual responsible has been identified where possible. In the case of individual developers, we refer to them using their GitHub or FarmHack user profile, with direct links to their profiles included in the catalogue for transparency and traceability. For institutional or project-based solutions, the name of the program, company, or research initiative is provided.

A major outcome of this iteration’s refinement was the recognition that while a large number of ADSs are hosted in public repositories and make their source code openly available, many of these lack an explicit open-source license. This is a significant concern, as the absence of a license does not imply permissive use. This widespread misconception that “no license” equals openness can hinder safe reuse, reproduction, and adaptation of otherwise valuable digital tools. Therefore, we strongly recommend that users of such solutions contact the developers or repository maintainers before deploying or modifying the software, particularly in commercial or institutional contexts. Among the solutions that do specify licenses, we observed a broad range of open-source license types. Common permissive licenses such as the MIT License, Apache-2.0, BSD-3-Clause, and EUPL-1.2 were frequently used, supporting flexible reuse and modification with minimal restrictions. More restrictive copyleft licenses, including AGPL-3.0, GPL-3.0, and LGPL-3.0, were also present, especially in software that is part of larger ecosystems or tools requiring reciprocal openness. These licenses ensure that derivative works remain open-source, contributing back to the community. A small subset of solutions included in the catalogue were identified as “open source” in related documentation or project outputs, but no public repository could be located after an extensive search. These were still included due to their relevance, technological value, or institutional backing (e.g., within EC-funded projects), but we clearly flag such cases in the catalogue. Their inclusion serves both as a placeholder and as an invitation for further clarification from developers or future iterations. This licensing and repository audit represents a key layer of due diligence in curating the catalogue, ensuring that users have both a functional and legal understanding of how each ADS can be applied. By improving the transparency of origin, licensing, and access, this section supports better-informed adoption and integration of open-source solutions across the agricultural sector.

3.2. Complete solutions

The updated catalogue features a selection of complete Open Source Software Agricultural Digital Solutions (ADSs) that offer fully functional tools for direct deployment. These solutions are developed to address key agricultural production steps—such as fertilization, irrigation, pest management, livestock management—as well as holistic farm management. Designed for practical use by farmers, advisors, and developers, they provide end-to-end capabilities that do not require significant further development. Each entry includes a description of the solution’s main functionalities and use cases, along with relevant technical details such as connectivity requirements. These complete solutions represent some of the most mature and applicable technologies in the catalogue and are central to the deployment and operationalization of digital farming practices across diverse agricultural contexts.

3.2.1. Fertilization updated Solutions

The fertilization-focused solutions in the catalogue support more efficient and sustainable nutrient management practices. These tools assist users in optimizing fertilizer use based on crop needs, environmental conditions, and decision models. The solutions vary in complexity—from lightweight edge-based systems to cloud-connected platforms offering AI-driven recommendations.

FaST (European Commission’s DG Agriculture and Rural Development, EU Space Program (DG DEFIS) and by the EU ISA2 Program (DG DIGIT), 2021): This cloud-based platform focuses on fertilization and is designed for use by farmers, advisors, and developers. Supported by DG DEFIS, DG DIGIT, and the European Commission’s DG Agriculture and Rural Development, FaST leverages space data (Copernicus and Galileo) and other public and private datasets to provide sustainable and competitive agricultural solutions. It supports the use of machine learning for image recognition, IoT data, various public sector data, and user-generated data, creating a modular platform to aid EU agriculture and the Common Agricultural Policy.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Requires cloud connectivity for accessing fertilization data, models, and services.)

Agstack Field Carbon model (Linux Foundation, 2023): The AgStack Field Carbon Model enables field-level carbon flux estimation by adapting NASA’s Soil Moisture Active Passive (SMAP) Level 4 Carbon (L4C) model for agricultural applications. Designed for farmers, advisors, and developers, the model facilitates measurement, reporting, and verification (MRV) of carbon sequestration efforts, supporting participation in carbon credit markets. The Python-based system can be deployed on cloud platforms and integrates with public or private data sources, promoting scalable and transparent carbon accounting in agriculture.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Cloud-based model for tracking carbon footprints in farming, requiring connectivity for calculations.)

Farm Advisory Tool for Nutrients (SATIVUM) (HE QUANTIFARM, 2025). SATIVUM is a decision support system (DSS) developed to enhance nutrient management for wheat cultivation in the Mediterranean region. Tailored for farmers and agricultural advisors, it provides agri-environmental monitoring tools to optimize fertilization practices, aiming to improve crop yield and environmental sustainability. The platform operates as a cloud-based solution, facilitating accessible and efficient nutrient management strategies.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Online platform.)

AgroNest (Github user: VeenathT, 2025): AgroNest is a full-featured MERN stack web application designed to manage all aspects of fertilizer logistics and soil health analytics. The platform supports fertilizer

buying/selling, dealer rating, lab management, soil testing integration, and personalized fertilizer recommendations. It offers dashboards for administrators, local dealer discovery for farmers, and promotional content tools. With a modular React frontend and Node.js/Express backend, it enhances decision-making, transparency, and productivity across the agricultural supply chain.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Internet access required for cloud-based application).

Fertilizer-Management-System (Github user: W-P-N, 2025): This is a lightweight database management system for retail-level fertilizer and pesticide tracking, built using Python, HTML, and CSS. The system allows entry and management of fertilizer and pesticide stock and supports basic UI interfaces using Flask templates. It's structured for small-scale agricultural retail operations and showcases a simple CRUD-style DBMS project.

Connectivity Requirements: None (Fully local; no internet required)

Fertilizer Distribution Management System (Github user: chamathamarsinghe96, 2025): This is a PHP and MySQL-based web application designed for managing the distribution of subsidized fertilizer to farmers. The system enables agricultural officers to register farmers, manage cultivation records, issue fertilizer, and monitor distribution records via a user-friendly interface. It includes features like farmer lookup, land registration, officer login, and integrates with a local database for recordkeeping—ideal for public sector or institutional deployment.

Connectivity Requirements: None (Fully local; no internet required)

Harvestify (Github user: Gladiator07, 2025): Harvestify is a machine learning–powered web platform that offers three key services: crop recommendation, fertilizer guidance, and plant disease diagnosis. Built using Python, Flask, and deep learning models, the system predicts the best crop to grow based on soil nutrient inputs, suggests fertilizers based on deficiencies, and identifies plant diseases via leaf image uploads. It's an educational proof-of-concept for integrating AI in precision agriculture, complete with notebooks and deployment via Heroku.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Internet required for cloud-based application)

Crop Management System (Github user: ab007shetty, 2025): Crop Management System is a comprehensive, ML-based decision support platform designed to help farmers with crop planning and nutrient management. Built using Python, PHP, and Scikit-learn, it offers crop prediction, fertilizer recommendations, rainfall forecasting, and yield estimation. The interface is web-based (Apache + PHP), using datasets with environmental and agronomic features like soil nutrients, pH, humidity, and seasonal data. It supports user input to generate real-time recommendations using multiple models.

Connectivity Requirements: None (Fully local; no internet required)

CropFusionAI (Github user: deepeshdm, 2025): CropFusionAI is a modern web-based decision support system for farmers, combining machine learning with intuitive design. It recommends optimal crops and fertilizers based on real-time inputs like soil type, humidity, rainfall, and nutrient levels. The backend is powered by FastAPI and LightGBM models, while the ReactJS frontend features interactive 3D visualization.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Internet required for cloud-based application)

AgriGo (Github user: kaymen99, 2025): AgriGo is an AI-powered web application that supports farmers in three critical areas: crop recommendation, fertilizer optimization, and plant disease detection. Built with Flask, TensorFlow, and scikit-learn, it analyzes soil and environmental inputs (e.g., NPK levels, pH, temperature, rainfall) to suggest the most suitable crops and fertilizer plans. It also features image-based

disease identification using a deep learning model trained on leaf images. AgriGo is designed for local use or containerized deployment via Docker.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Internet required for cloud-based application)

Eco-fertilization (Github user: Gekko12, 2025): Eco-fertilization is a rainfall-aware nutrient recommendation system designed to guide farmers in applying the right fertilizer mix for optimal crop growth while minimizing runoff and nutrient loss. Built with Flask and scikit-learn, it uses a random forest model trained on time-series rainfall and crop data to suggest optimal N-P-K ratios. The system provides alerts, integrates 7-day weather forecasts, and displays results in a browser via a local web server.

Connectivity Requirements: None (Local deployment; no internet required)

Agromatic (Github user: nicolapace, 2025): Agromatic is a simulation environment for autonomous agricultural robots performing soil fertilization in open fields. Built on ROS (Robot Operating System) and Gazebo, it enables researchers to test navigation algorithms using AMCL, custom goal dispatching, and map-based path planning. It simulates a robot (Husky platform) navigating dynamically in farm-like conditions and includes Python and C++ nodes for managing motion, obstacle detection, and fertilization routes.

Connectivity Requirements: None (Local deployment; no internet required)

3.2.2. Irrigation updated Solutions

The catalogue features a diverse set of open-source software solutions dedicated to improving irrigation management. These tools enable better control over water application by leveraging automation, sensor integration, and in some cases, weather or soil data analytics. The solutions range from lightweight edge-deployable applications for offline use to more complex cloud-based systems requiring continuous connectivity.

FluxePi (Fruxefarms, 2019):. FluxePi is a Raspberry Pi–based dashboard for automating and monitoring indoor agriculture environments, with a particular focus on irrigation control. Built on a LAMP stack, it collects sensor data and manages grow operations such as lighting, ventilation, and watering via connected relays. The platform features real-time and historical monitoring of temperature, humidity, and soil moisture, as well as manual and scheduled irrigation management. Additional tools include camera feeds, crop journals, user access control, and activity logging, all accessible through a web browser on the local network.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Internet-dependent irrigation system for indoor farming, requiring cloud connectivity.)

AgIoT (SmartFarming project, 2020): AgIoT is a modular IoT platform developed under the SmartFarming and Water4Ever projects, focused on optimizing irrigation in precision agriculture. Designed for integration with both conventional and smart farming machinery, it supports real-time monitoring of soil moisture, plant health, and environmental conditions through embedded sensors. The system enables variable-rate irrigation, NPK management, and in-field automation, using data from sensors and GNSS technologies like Galileo and EGNOS for spatial accuracy. AgIoT is built to be interoperable with standards such as ISOBUS and FIWARE, facilitating scalable, sustainable water management across diverse farming contexts.

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (Designed for IoT-based smart farming; some features work with minimal connectivity.)

AgIoT Purdue University(Github user: 2021-Thomas, 2025): AgIoT is a student-built precision agriculture solution designed to address irrigation challenges during natural disasters such as tornadoes. Developed at Purdue and Dongguk universities, the system combines soil moisture sensors, LoRa communication, and a cloud-based control platform using Node-RED and MariaDB. It calculates irrigation priorities using a cost-effective algorithm that considers battery status, distance to water sources, and real-time moisture data. Built on Arduino microcontrollers and serverless cloud functions, it targets low-cost, energy-efficient deployment in emergency contexts.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (requires Node-RED, LoRaWAN gateway, and server/db access)

Smart AgroSensor for Irrigation Applications (Universidad de Ibagué, 2021. Murcia-Moreno, H. et.al. 2018): Smart AgroSensor is an intelligent irrigation decision support system built using low-cost agroclimatic sensors and machine learning. Designed for deployment on farms, the system uses an Arduino Mega 2560 and Raspberry Pi 3 to monitor variables such as soil moisture and light levels. It supports both manual and automatic irrigation modes and includes a web-based control interface. Python-based scripts facilitate data logging, model training with scikit-learn, and real-time irrigation decisions, making it an adaptable and affordable platform for precision irrigation in small-scale settings.

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (Works locally but benefits from internet connectivity for remote monitoring.)

Automated Irrigation System (Github user: PatrickHallek, 2025): This open-source irrigation system is built to be scalable, accurate, and durable for real-world agricultural use. Designed with ESP8266, Raspberry Pi, capacitive soil sensors, and relays, the system triggers watering based on custom soil moisture thresholds. It features a responsive web dashboard for real-time data visualization, irrigation scheduling, and manual overrides. The project includes full hardware and software setup instructions.

Connectivity Requirements: None (Edge-based, fully operational offline without internet dependency.)

SIP (Sustainable Irrigation Platform) (Github user: Dan-in-CA, 2025): SIP is a powerful, open-source irrigation controller built for the Raspberry Pi. It provides a multilingual web interface for managing sprinkler, drip, or hydroponic systems from any browser. With a modular plugin architecture, SIP supports automation via HTTP, MQTT, and Node-RED. It's ideal for DIY setups and supports integration with various relay boards and GPIO-compatible hardware for scalable, precise irrigation management.

Connectivity Requirements: None (Edge-based irrigation control with local decision-making, fully offline.)

OpenSprinkler (OpenSprinkler, 2025): OpenSprinkler is a unified open-source firmware for smart irrigation controllers compatible with the OpenSprinkler hardware ecosystem (standalone, Pi-based, or Linux). It provides a web interface, supports scheduling, weather-based automation, and integrates with APIs like Weather Underground. Designed for extensibility and automation, OpenSprinkler helps optimize water usage while offering local and cloud-based control for residential or agricultural irrigation systems.

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (Works locally, with optional cloud features requiring internet access.)

Smart Irrigation Controller (Github user: GerruG, 2025): This IoT-based irrigation system uses an ESP32 microcontroller paired with sensors (soil moisture, temperature, light) and a Raspberry Pi server to automate and monitor watering. It features a secure Netbird VPN connection, a responsive web dashboard, and a React Native mobile app. Designed for real-time soil analysis and efficient water use, the system includes data logging, token-based API security, and potential for cloud integration.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (Hybrid system requiring occasional internet access for remote monitoring.)

IoT-Based Smart Irrigation System (Github user: jatinggrwl, 2025): This Arduino and ESP8266-based smart irrigation project automates pump control based on real-time field data. It integrates sensors (soil moisture, rain, temperature, humidity, flame) and communicates via ThingSpeak cloud. A Twilio API is used to send SMS alerts when rain is detected, and the system can be remotely managed via an Android app built in Android Studio. It's a complete IoT-enabled solution for small-scale smart farming.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (Cloud-connected irrigation system with moderate connectivity requirements.)

RoboRiego IoT Irrigation System (Github user: alexaGonLuc16, 2025): RoboRiego is an eco-friendly IoT-based smart irrigation system that integrates ESP32 microcontrollers, the MQTT communication protocol, and Python automation. Designed to remotely monitor and control irrigation, it includes modules for camera streaming, soil analysis, color detection, and motor control. It supports modular expansion and real-time decision-making, making it ideal for precision agriculture and garden automation.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (IoT-based system requiring internet connectivity for full functionality.)

GardenPI (Github user: ankitr42, 2025): GardenPI is a Raspberry Pi-based automated watering system designed for home gardens. It runs on Raspbian and can be deployed even on a Raspberry Pi Zero. The system includes a web interface for remote control and monitoring, making it easy to manage irrigation while away. It's a fully offline-capable, DIY-friendly project suitable for tech-savvy gardeners looking to automate their plant care.

Connectivity Requirements: None (Fully offline, operates locally without internet dependency.)

Pirrigo (Github user: vacovsky, 2025): Pirrigo is a full-featured irrigation management system built with Go and Angular, designed for Raspberry Pi. It enables users to manually or automatically control irrigation zones, track water usage, and estimate monthly costs. Integrated with Weather Underground, Pirrigo adjusts schedules based on real-time weather data. It includes a web app for visualization and management, offering charts, scheduling, and hardware status monitoring—all tailored for smart garden automation.

Connectivity Requirements: None (Local processing-based irrigation controller with no connectivity requirements.)

Moisture Monitor (Github user: AbhijnanPrakash, 2025): This project introduces a low-cost, smart irrigation system using Arduino Uno and various sensors (moisture, temperature, rain) to automate watering for small-scale farmers. Designed to be economical and sustainable, it replaces expensive controllers and includes basic pump control for soil and plant health. The system helps conserve water and improve yields, making it suitable for rural or smallholder agricultural contexts.

Connectivity Requirements: None (Works completely offline with local processing.)

Irrigation-Pi (Github user: max-pfeiffer, 2025): Irrigation-Pi is a Python and Angular-based web application that turns a Raspberry Pi into a full-featured irrigation controller. It supports relay boards (e.g., Waveshare), offers schedule-based and live relay switching, system monitoring, and mobile-friendly web access. The backend is built with FastAPI and supports RESTful APIs, while the frontend is optimized for responsive use. It runs fully offline and even supports hosting via a local Wi-Fi hotspot.

Connectivity Requirements: None (Edge-based irrigation monitoring, fully operational offline.)

Irrigation Controller (Github user: mwick83, 2025): This ESP32-based smart irrigation system is designed for flexible, autonomous plant watering. It supports interval-based scheduling, reservoir monitoring, and conditional logic like skipping watering on rainy days. Built for balcony gardens, it integrates a relay system and sensor inputs via UART and is optimized for low power usage, with future plans for solar power. The project emphasizes reliability and modularity for DIY gardeners.

Connectivity Requirements: None (Local operation with no internet connectivity needed.)

Open-Rain (Github user: eloialonso, 2025): Open-Rain is a DIY Raspberry Pi-powered irrigation system offering two core modes: manual on-demand watering through a web interface, and scheduled irrigation via cron jobs. It uses a solenoid valve, ultrasonic water-level sensor, and MySQL-based web dashboard. The system is fully autonomous, having been tested in hot, dry environments, and supports both local and remote operation for small gardens or experimental setups.

Connectivity Requirements: None (Works fully offline with optional cloud integration.)

Smart Irrigation System with FC-28 (Github user: deysarkarswarup, 2025): This project demonstrates interfacing the FC-28 soil moisture sensor with an Arduino to build a basic smart irrigation system. The FC-28 provides both analog and digital output, enabling flexible moisture detection. When soil moisture falls below a set threshold, the system activates irrigation automatically. It's a lightweight, educational solution for introducing automation in small-scale or experimental agriculture.

Connectivity Requirements: None (Edge-based system with local moisture sensing and decision-making, fully offline.)

IrrigationSystem (Github user: blsd1512, 2025): This project is a team-developed, open-source irrigation system utilizing ESP8266 microcontrollers and MQTT for wireless communication. Designed with modular components like a custom PCB, web-based dashboard, and SQL Server database, it supports real-time control and monitoring. The system aims to promote sustainable irrigation practices and is structured to support future AI-based enhancements.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium/Flexible (requires MQTT)

ESP32 Automatic Irrigation API (Github user: Isacco-B, 2025): This project is an MQTT-based API designed to run on an ESP32 microcontroller, enabling remote control and monitoring of irrigation systems. It supports zone activation, real-time status updates, and the creation of automated watering schedules. Developed entirely in Python, the system allows lightweight, responsive communication for IoT-enabled agricultural setups using microservices architecture.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium/Flexible (requires MQTT)

IoTGreenGuardian Agriculture Automation System (Github user: roycuadra, 2025): IoTGreenGuardian is a cloud-based smart irrigation system using NodeMCU ESP-12E and sensors like DHT11 and soil moisture detectors. It automates watering through a motor and relay based on real-time environmental data. The system integrates with ThingSpeak for cloud monitoring and features an OLED display for local feedback. It aims to optimize water usage and growing conditions via IoT technologies.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (requires ThingSpeak)

ML-Based Fog-Cloud Agricultural Irrigation System (Github user: duanepm, 2025): This smart irrigation platform integrates Arduino, Raspberry Pi (as a fog node), Firebase, and machine learning to optimize water use. It features automatic and manual irrigation modes, sensor-based real-time decision-making, and a

neural network model for irrigation prediction. A mobile app built with MIT App Inventor enables remote control. The system supports data preprocessing on the Pi before syncing to the cloud for efficient and scalable agriculture automation.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (cloud-based predictions)

Smart Irrigation System using ML and IoT (Github user: Avdhesh616, 2025): This smart irrigation system uses a NodeMCU with DHT11 and soil moisture sensors, connected to the ThingSpeak IoT cloud. A Python-based central controller retrieves real-time data, gathers precipitation info via API, and uses a Random Forest ML model to predict optimal soil moisture. It accounts for crop type and day/night conditions (via LDR) to control irrigation efficiently. The system supports remote monitoring and dynamic, data-driven water management for precision farming.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (ThingSpeak cloud platform, Python API)

OpenAgri irrigation management (OpenAgri, 2025): The “OpenAgri Irrigation Service” acts as a toolkit, providing a set of useful calculators to support decision-making in irrigation management. The current implementation of the OpenAgri Irrigation Service is designed to offer an “Evapotranspiration calculator (ETo)” and a “Soil moisture analysis engine”. More info at: <https://horizon-openagri.eu/os-solutions/>

Connectivity Requirements: Medium/Flexible (periodic internet access to obtain weather forecasts and soil moisture data; some functionalities may be available offline.)

3.2.3. Pest management updated Solutions

The pest management solutions in the catalogue offer digital tools to support early detection, monitoring, and decision-making for pest control. These open-source software tools include both AI-driven detection systems and decision support platforms that help reduce crop losses and optimize pesticide use. They range from fully offline edge-based applications to hybrid or cloud-based systems requiring regular connectivity for model updates or remote processing.

Agstack Pest models (Linux Foundation, 2023): Provides pest management models to help farmers control pests effectively. These models offer predictive analytics and data-driven strategies to manage pest populations, reducing crop losses and improving yield quality.

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (Pest prediction models that can work offline, with periodic cloud sync for updates.)

Insect Detect (Sittinger et. Al., 2025) is a DIY camera trap system for automated insect monitoring. Built using affordable hardware like the Raspberry Pi Zero 2 W and Luxonis OAK-1, it integrates YOLOv5–v8 models for object detection. The system runs Python scripts to capture and analyze insect activity and is designed to operate offline with optional cloud syncing for data uploads.

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (Edge-based detection; can work offline but benefits from cloud updates.)

Wadhvani AI Pest Management (Wadhvani AI, 2025): This project by Wadhvani AI provides an open dataset of pest images tailored for developing pest recognition models in cotton farming. The repository includes pre-annotated data with bounding boxes and tools for preprocessing and formatting datasets for

use with machine learning frameworks like PyTorch or TensorFlow. It's a foundational resource for building AI solutions in agricultural pest detection.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium/Flexible (Hybrid model; works on edge devices but syncs data periodically with cloud storage.)

Insect Detection on Sticky Traps (Github user: checolag, 2025) This project provides detection models and Python scripts for identifying *Scaphoideus titanus* and *Orientus ishidae* on yellow sticky traps. It supports YOLOv8 and Detectron2 frameworks and includes utilities for k-fold cross-validation, image augmentation, and model evaluation. Ideal for research in automated pest monitoring, it allows fully offline local processing.

Connectivity Requirements: None (Works on local edge devices without internet connectivity.)

Smart Agricultural Pest Management System (Github user: 18hyacinthe, 2025): This project leverages machine learning and IoT to support farmers in real-time pest monitoring. It uses an EfficientNetV2 model trained on a diverse dataset to detect pests via webcam video feeds. Key features include live video inference, real-time notifications, and pest classification using deep learning. Designed for practical deployment, it offers immediate visual feedback and email alerts when pests are detected.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (Uses both edge processing and cloud-based analytics, requiring occasional connectivity.)

Advanced Pest Detection System (Github user: Ali-Rizvi-1, 2025): This system combines RGB and thermal imaging with environmental data and GPS tracking to detect agricultural pests. It uses YOLOv8 for object detection on both image types, fuses the outputs for improved accuracy, and optionally stores results in the cloud. The modular architecture includes pest detection, image capture, and location modules, and is designed for flexible deployment and extensibility.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (Cloud-assisted pest detection, requiring internet access for remote data processing.)

Pest Classification and Detection System (Github user: NikhilAMathew, 2025): This project uses deep convolutional neural networks to identify and classify crop pests based on images. Built with Flask, PyTorch, and MongoDB, the system includes a web-based interface for farmers and agricultural officers to view pest types, suggested pesticides, and submit queries. Designed for scalability and offline or online image capture, it supports rapid, accurate, and user-friendly pest detection for sustainable agriculture.

Connectivity Requirements: None (Runs locally with deep learning models and does not require internet.)

BioMA (Biophysical Model Applications) (Donatelli et al., 2025): BioMA is a modular, open-source software framework developed for creating and running biophysical models in agriculture and environmental research. Built in C# on the .NET platform, it allows for flexible, component-based simulations of crop growth, pest dynamics, soil behavior, and climate impacts. It's widely used by the European Commission and research initiatives like MODEXTREME to assess agricultural productivity and climate adaptation strategies.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (Mixed deployment; requires periodic internet access for model updates.)

Pest Detection using Deep Learning (Github user: shivam1423, 2025): This project provides a complete pipeline for detecting agricultural pests using TensorFlow from scratch. It includes Jupyter notebooks for model training and inference, a custom pest dataset, and scripts to convert annotations into TFRecord

format. The model uses a frozen TensorFlow object detection graph, and all outputs are saved locally after inference, making it suitable for offline or local use.

Connectivity Requirements: None (Runs deep learning models locally without any internet dependency.)

Agricultural Pests Management (Github user: rahulkundelwalll, 2025): This project implements a real-time pest monitoring system using the EfficientNetV2B0 deep learning model. Trained on a diverse Kaggle dataset of pest images (e.g., ants, beetles, caterpillars, snails), the model performs live inference on webcam feeds using OpenCV. The system overlays detected pest classifications directly onto the video, helping farmers make fast, informed decisions in the field.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (Works with both local processing and cloud-based insights, requiring occasional connectivity.)

OpenAgri pest and disease management (OpenAgri, 2025): The “OpenAgri Pest and Disease Management service” offers a modular pest infestation probabilistic decision support system. It receives as input a number of relevant variables such as weather conditions, crop type, growth stage, and observations from scouting, in order to provide an estimate of the risk of pest and disease infestation. Initially, algorithms tailored to the pests and diseases of the OpenAgri SIPs are implemented, aiming to act as examples for guiding the development of rule-based prediction systems for additional plant enemies. More info at: <https://horizon-openagri.eu/os-solutions/>

Connectivity Requirements: Moderate (Requires regular internet access for data inputs like weather conditions and for updating pest and disease models; limited offline functionality.)

3.2.4. Livestock updated Solutions

The livestock solutions in the catalogue focus on monitoring, managing, and improving animal health, productivity, and farm operations. These open-source tools support functions such as heat stress detection, weight estimation, farm record-keeping, and livestock tracking. The solutions vary in technical setup, from edge-based systems designed for offline use to cloud-dependent platforms requiring consistent connectivity for data storage and analysis.

Livestocktracker (Github user: DigiBanks99, 2025): Livestocktracker is a web-based livestock management application designed to track animal data on farms and generate detailed reports. Built with a modern stack using Angular (frontend) and .NET Core (backend), it allows for the registration of livestock, health monitoring, and performance tracking. The system supports centralized recordkeeping and aims to assist farmers in optimizing herd health and productivity through structured data management.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (requires internet to access cloud-hosted database and backend services)

BovHEAT (Plenio et.al., 2021): BovHEAT is an tool for automated heat detection in dairy cattle using SCR Heatime neck-mounted activity monitors. It processes raw sensor data to identify estrus cycles, performs error correction, and outputs reports in both XLSX and PDF formats. The software supports custom threshold settings and observation periods, making it suitable for veterinarians, researchers, and farm managers aiming to improve reproductive efficiency through behavioral monitoring.

Connectivity Requirements: None (local edge processing)

Livestock Management System (Github user: vikram0230, 2025): Livestock Management System is a desktop application developed in Python with a GUI for managing farm animals, including goats. It allows farmers to track individual animals, generate alerts for vaccinations and breeding readiness, and manage financial records related to livestock commerce. The system is modular, with separate interfaces for animal registration, finance tracking, vaccination scheduling, and health monitoring.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (depends on online database and cloud storage)

HerdNet (Delplanque et. al. 2023): HerdNet is a deep learning-based aerial animal detection and counting system tailored for wildlife and livestock monitoring. It processes high-resolution imagery to identify and count herds using object detection models trained on diverse habitats like savannas and deserts. The system supports bounding box annotation formats, pretrained models, and reproducible pipelines via conda environments. Originally developed for academic research, it has been applied to species including buffalo, elephants, and goats using aerial and drone imagery.

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (operates on edge for local processing)

LiveStock (Github user: pedroenriquedev, 2025): LiveStock is a modern herd analytics platform built to help farmers manage cattle inventory, track animal growth, and monitor financial performance. Developed using Next.js (frontend) and Express/MongoDB (backend), the system supports adding individual animals, logging weights, managing pastures, and simulating sales. It includes data visualization with React ChartJS and provides full CRUD API access. Originally built for personal use, it's now publicly available and deployable via Vercel.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (requires cloud-based database for management)

Pig Weight Estimation (Pixel Occupancy Analysis) (Github user: nikmomo, 2025): This project explores estimating pig weight using depth imagery and pixel occupancy analysis. It uses image datasets labeled with actual weights and processes them through Jupyter notebooks implementing linear regression and XGBoost models. The approach assigns depth-based pixel weights to calculate total estimated mass, enabling scalable, camera-based livestock monitoring. Designed for resource-limited settings, it can operate offline and be extended to other livestock species.

Connectivity Requirements: None (local edge processing)

KAMADHENU (Github user: MautKaFarishta, 2025): KAMADHENU is a lightweight mobile application (APK size ~8MB) developed using Flutter, designed to assist livestock owners in managing cattle information. The app enables users to add and track cattle details efficiently. It features multilingual support and incorporates speech-to-text functionality, catering especially to users with limited literacy.

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (operates primarily offline; internet needed for language updates and speech-to-text services)

eFarm (Github user: peter-evance, 2025): eFarm is a precision agriculture web application developed using Python (Django) for the backend and TypeScript (Angular) for the frontend. The platform is designed to assist farmers in managing dairy and poultry operations by facilitating data-driven decisions. It offers modules for tracking livestock health, feed management, and production metrics. The system is structured to support expansion into other sectors, such as swine farming.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (requires cloud-based database for farm data storage)

Poultry Farming Management System (Github user: Musanza, 2025): This web-based application is designed to assist poultry farmers in managing their operations more efficiently. Developed using PHP and CSS, the system automates the recording of essential farm data, including bird inventory, egg production, sales, and expenses. By replacing traditional manual ledger systems, it streamlines data entry, facilitates report generation, and supports better decision-making for farm management.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (requires continuous cloud-based database access)

3.2.5. Farm management updated Solutions

The farm management solutions in the catalogue provide comprehensive digital support for organizing and optimizing agricultural operations. These platforms enable users to plan, record, monitor, and analyze farm activities, often covering both crop and livestock systems. The solutions include both lightweight tools suitable for smaller farms and modular platforms designed for broader scalability. Connectivity requirements vary, with some tools operating fully offline and others requiring continuous internet access to leverage cloud-based functionalities.

Sen4Cap (ESA, DG-Agri, DG-Grow, & DG-JRC. 2021): This solution focuses on farm management and agricultural practices monitoring. Developed by DG-Agri, DG-Grow, and DG-JRC, it provides validated algorithms, products, workflows, and best practices for agriculture monitoring relevant for the management of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). Sen4Cap aims to modernize and simplify CAP management by leveraging Sentinel-derived information for better agricultural monitoring and decision-making.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Uses satellite data and cloud-based analytics for monitoring agricultural practices. Requires continuous internet access.)

farmOS (FarmOS, 2025): farmOS is a web-based application for farm management, planning, and record keeping. Developed by a community of farmers, developers, and researchers, it provides a standard platform for agricultural data collection and management. Built on Drupal, farmOS is modular, extensible, and secure, supporting various agricultural activities including crop and livestock management, equipment tracking, and mapping. The platform also offers the farmOS Field Kit, a progressive web app for offline data entry, enhancing its utility in the field.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Cloud-based farm management system; requires constant internet access for real-time record-keeping.)

FarmMaps (AKKERWEB FOUNDATION, 2025): FarmMaps is a cloud-based farm management platform developed by the Akkerweb Foundation, designed to support precision agriculture through a suite of applications and data services. The platform enables farmers, advisors, and developers to store and manage farm data securely, while offering tools for decision support and on-farm cycle optimization. FarmMaps integrates various data sources, including satellite imagery, soil maps, and weather data, and provides access to agronomic models such as Watbal for water availability, Tipstar for potato growth, Blight for late blight infection, and Nemadece for nematode management. These models are accessible via APIs, facilitating the development of customized applications tailored to specific crops and regions.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Web-based farm management platform that relies on cloud storage and processing.)

Crop Planning Software (Github user: Carter, C. 2025): CropPlanning is a cross-platform desktop application designed to assist small farmers and market gardeners in managing complex crop schedules and planting

plans. The software offers a spreadsheet-like interface that allows users to create, duplicate, and manage crops and plantings, with features such as automatic calculations for seeding and transplanting schedules, yield estimations, and seed quantity requirements. Additional functionalities include weekly planting lists, greenhouse tray tracking, and customizable field and bed configurations. Although no longer actively maintained, the application remains functional and continues to be utilized by many in the agricultural community.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Needs internet access for cloud-based crop planning and data storage.)

FarmBot OS Web app (FarmBot, 2025): FarmBot Web App is a browser-based interface that enables users to design, automate, and monitor precision farming tasks for CNC-based garden systems. Key features include a drag-and-drop farm designer, real-time manual controls, and tools for creating sequences and regimens to automate operations like watering and weeding. The platform also supports camera integration for weed detection and provides detailed logging of device activity. Users can access the hosted version at my.farm.bot or self-host via the open-source codebase.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Requires constant cloud connectivity for remote farm automation and control.)

Litefarm (Centre for Sustainable Food Systems at the University of British Columbia, 2025): LiteFarm is a community-led digital platform built to support small- and medium-scale farmers in managing their farms with a focus on environmental sustainability, social responsibility, and economic viability. It provides tools for planning and recording farming activities such as planting, harvesting, and input use, while also supporting organic certification, worker safety, and ecosystem service tracking. The platform is multilingual, mobile-friendly, and co-designed with farmers and researchers to ensure real-world relevance and accessibility across diverse geographies.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Cloud-based farm management tool; requires internet access for logging and retrieving farm data.)

Ekylibre (Ekylibre. 2025):. Ekylibre is an open-source farm management information system (FMIS) developed to streamline agricultural operations through a unified platform. It supports a wide range of features including crop and livestock tracking, accounting, inventory, and sales management. Built on Ruby on Rails and Ember.js, Ekylibre is designed for farmers, advisors, and developers alike. Its modular architecture and AGPL license encourage adaptability, and the system is available as both self-hosted and cloud-based deployments. It is especially tailored for European compliance and data interoperability, making it suitable for farms of all sizes and types.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Cloud-based farm management software with dependency on online access for full functionality.)

AgStack Asset Registry 1.0/2.0 (Linux Foundation, 2025): AgStack Asset Registry is a backend service that registers geospatial assets—typically polygons representing fields or plots—and generates a unique 256-bit alphanumeric identifier for each. Designed to support interoperability across agricultural systems, the tool enables the standardization of land-based asset identification for use in farm registries, digital services, or regulatory platforms. The system is built in Python and includes API services, containerized deployment with Docker, and scripts for automated processing and logging.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Cloud-based agricultural asset management system. Needs continuous internet access.)

Agstack Weather Server (Linux Foundation, 2025): AgStack Weather Server is a backend service for ingesting, preprocessing, and serving historical weather data relevant to agricultural applications. It supports API-based access to weather histories by location, delivering clean, tabular data sourced from multiple datasets, including Multi-Sensor QPE, NLDAS-2, and NOAA archives. The system handles data resolution, substitution for missing values, and grid-based spatial processing to deliver high-quality weather information where possible. It is designed for integration into agricultural platforms that require localized climate data for decision-making.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Requires internet access to fetch weather data for farm management applications.)

Agstack Ag-rec (Linux Foundation, 2025): AgRec is a prototype recommendation platform that aggregates and delivers agricultural best practices provided by Cooperative Extension Services. It uses Elasticsearch, Kibana, and Enterprise App Search to store, manage, and serve data related to crops, practices, and regions. Users can access recommendations through a browser-based Search UI or via API endpoints. The system is designed to scale as a shared resource for local and global farming communities, with ongoing development toward structured data pipelines and broader integration.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Relies on cloud-based agricultural record-keeping, requiring stable internet access.)

Tania (Tanibox, 2025): Tania is a lightweight farm management system designed to support smallholder and hobbyist farmers in tracking core agricultural activities. It offers features to manage farm areas, tasks, reservoirs, crop progress, and inventories through a clean and local-first interface. Built using Go and Node.js, the application runs as a compiled binary with SQLite or MySQL for data storage. It provides a RESTful API for integration with other tools or mobile clients, and is designed for flexible, offline-first deployment without requiring additional web server infrastructure.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Requires continuous cloud access for real-time farm management.)

Agrosense (Murcia-Moreno, H. et.al. 2018): AgroSense is an IoT-based crop monitoring system designed to capture real-time agrometeorological data through a distributed sensor network. The platform consists of solar-powered slave nodes that gather environmental variables from the field and transmit them via ZigBee to a master station with internet connectivity. Data is published online using 3G communication for remote access. The system includes signal conditioning, software filters, early warning protocols, and battery management features. Originally developed to support climate adaptation strategies in rice farming in Colombia's Tolima region, it serves as a foundational model for low-cost, open-field environmental monitoring.

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (Designed for local farm monitoring, but data syncs with the cloud when available.)

Farm Data Relay System (Github user: TimmBogner, 2025): Farm Data Relay System (FDRS) enables long-range, low-power communication between agricultural sensors and gateways in remote environments without relying on WiFi or LoRaWAN infrastructure. The system leverages ESP-NOW and LoRa protocols to connect sensor nodes and controllers to modular gateway devices that route data using serial, LoRa, or MQTT. FDRS supports repeaters for extended coverage, and is suitable for real-time sensor networks in fields lacking broadband connectivity. Designed with Arduino-compatible hardware in mind, it includes example sketches for sensor nodes, gateways, and MQTT integration.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Provides broadband connectivity in remote farm locations, requiring strong internet access.)

OpenWeedLocator (OWL) (Coleman, G. et. al. 2022): OpenWeedLocator (OWL) is a low-cost, image-based weed detection device designed for site-specific weed control in both in-crop and fallow scenarios. It runs on a Raspberry Pi and uses simple green-detection algorithms with options for customization and upgrades. OWL integrates a camera system, relay control board, and optional 3D-printed enclosures, allowing it to activate solenoids, sprayers, or other 12V components for targeted weed treatment. The system supports real-time operation and has been field-tested on robots, vehicles, and bicycles, offering an accessible solution for precision weeding.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Uses cloud-based weed detection and mapping; requires strong connectivity.)

Open Food Network (Open Food Foundation, 2025): Open Food Network is a web-based platform that connects farmers, food hubs, cooperatives, and consumers through a digital marketplace for local food distribution. It enables the creation of online shops where producers can manage inventory, set prices, and coordinate logistics. Buyers can browse local offerings and purchase directly or through food hubs. The platform supports complex supply chains with tools for stock aggregation, order cycles, shipping, and payment processing. Built using Ruby on Rails, it is internationally maintained and deployed across multiple regions with strong community governance.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Cloud-based food distribution platform requiring continuous internet access.)

QuantiFarm Benchmarking of Farming Practices Tool (Quantifarm HE project, 2025): The QuantiFarm Benchmarking Tool is a web-based application for comparing digital agricultural solutions across key performance indicators. It allows users—typically researchers, advisors, or project evaluators—to input qualitative and quantitative data to benchmark farming practices against sustainability, economic, and technological criteria. Designed for use in EU-funded field trials and stakeholder workshops, the tool provides structured templates, flexible scoring, and visualization dashboards. It is part of the QuantiFarm initiative to standardize the assessment of digital agriculture impact in Europe.

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (Can be downloaded and used offline, but cloud features need periodic internet access.)

OpenAgri Farm Calendar (OpenAgri, 2025): The “OpenAgri Digital Farm Calendar” service aims to address the data capture needs of farms by providing for the manual recording of: farmers activities, farmers observations, parcels properties and the recording of the farm’s assets. A Web User Interface (UI) is provided which allows the users to visualize and navigate through the farm calendar of activities and to facilitate the management of the farm assets. In addition, all these operations and farm assets can be managed through a REST API, which provides these resources in a linked data format (i.e., using JSON-LD) and conforms to the OpenAgri Common Semantic Model (OCSM). More info at: <https://horizon-openagri.eu/os-solutions/>

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (Operates offline with reduced functionality; syncs with cloud services when online.)

OpenAgri weather-service (OpenAgri, 2025): The functionalities offered by the “OpenAgri Weather Data service” are based on the integration of open or low-cost weather monitoring and forecast services e.g., [OpenWeather](#), and also by connecting to local weather stations. A variety of agricultural weather data functionalities will progressively be integrated and offered for use, such as services for measuring the

accumulation of precipitation, dormant season’s accumulation of chilling hours, calculators of Growing Degree Days, forecasts and weather conditions in relation to optimum conditions per farming activity (e.g. spraying) and crop type. More info at: <https://horizon-openagri.eu/os-solutions/>

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (dependent on continuous internet connectivity to fetch real-time weather data from external APIs.)

OpenAgri reporting service (OpenAgri, 2025): The “OpenAgri Reporting service” enables (semi)automated reports generation aiming to significantly reduce reporting burdens towards a variety of stakeholders having as starting point the following indicative domains: a) generating farm level aggregates addressing policy needs (e.g. new CAP indicators, SAIO pesticide reporting), b) supporting certification (GlobalGAP, organic, etc.), c) other data and reporting required by contractual relations or track and trace legal obligations (e.g. Protected Designation of Origin-PDO). A set of reports are currently under development and will be available with both human and machine-readable outputs. More info at: <https://horizon-openagri.eu/os-solutions/>

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (Can generate reports offline using locally available datasets; internet access needed for data synchronization and sharing reports.)

3.3. Simpler Components

As mentioned, the catalogue also features a wide range of simpler open-source software components that provide specific functionalities to support the development or enhancement of Agricultural Digital Solutions (ADSs). These components include tools for IoT integration, data processing and analytics, weather and climate data services, geospatial mapping, farm management modules, and interoperability frameworks. They are particularly useful for developers and technical users who wish to build customized solutions or complement existing platforms.

3.3.1. Farm Management Tools

This subsection highlights simpler open-source components specifically designed to support various aspects of farm management. Unlike full-scale platforms, these tools typically focus on individual tasks such as field operations tracking, tillage and manure management, or digital record-keeping. They can be integrated into larger systems or used independently depending on the user’s technical capacity and needs. These components are particularly valuable for developers aiming to build modular or task-specific ADSs. Most of the tools are cloud-based or require periodic connectivity for data syncing, though some offer limited offline functionality.

FarmVibes.Connect (Microsoft, 2025): FarmVibes.Connect is an experimental connectivity platform developed by Microsoft Research to deliver long-range, low-cost internet access to remote farm areas. It uses underutilized TV white space spectrum (VHF/UHF bands) to provide broadband coverage directly in the field and supports narrowband IoT (NB-IoT) over the same spectrum for sensor communication. The system enables data transmission from drones, tractors, and edge devices even where traditional Wi-Fi or cellular service is unavailable. Designed for scalability, a single base station can cover tens of miles and hundreds of IoT endpoints, supporting high-density, sensor-rich agriculture.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (Operates on edge but requires periodic cloud connectivity for syncing)

FarmVibes.Edge (Microsoft, 2025): FarmVibes.Edge is a local edge-computing system designed to process large volumes of farm data—such as drone imagery and sensor inputs—directly on the farm, minimizing the need for high-speed internet connectivity. It runs AI, computer vision, and data fusion workloads on-site,

enabling real-time processing and decision-making. The platform supports stitching aerial images, detecting field anomalies, and intelligently routing data from edge to cloud. It is optimized for rural environments where bandwidth is limited, and aims to empower precision agriculture through local, AI-enabled computing.

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (Processes data locally on edge devices; requires occasional connectivity for updates.)

FarmVibes.Bot (Microsoft, 2025): FarmVibes.Bot is a chatbot-enabled communication platform designed to support digital advisory services for farmers, especially in rural and low-connectivity environments. It enables organizations to interact with users via SMS, USSD, and popular messaging apps such as WhatsApp, Facebook, and Telegram. The platform supports two-way communication for surveys, feedback collection, service linkage (e.g., financing or insurance), and data-driven advisory delivery. It also offers built-in data visualization for tracking user interactions and engagement. The system is actively used by over 500,000 farmers in sub-Saharan Africa.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Cloud-based farm management and communication tool requiring continuous connectivity.)

FarmVibes.AI (Microsoft, 2025): FarmVibes.AI is a modular, open-source framework for building geospatial machine learning models tailored to agriculture and sustainability. It supports the fusion of diverse spatiotemporal datasets—including satellite imagery (Sentinel-1/2, NAIP), drone data, elevation maps, and weather information—to generate robust insights such as carbon estimation, crop growth analysis, and farming practice detection. The platform includes tools for data ingestion, preprocessing, and model training, along with pre-built workflows and notebooks optimized for remote sensing and Earth observation tasks in agriculture.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Cloud-based AI-powered farm analytics, requiring continuous connectivity.)

OpenATK Tillage App (OpenATK, 2025): The OpenATK Tillage App is an Android-based mobile tool for recording and managing tillage operations across farm fields. It allows users to assign statuses such as “Planned,” “Started,” or “Done” to each tillage activity, while tracking additional data like operator name, comments, and the date of action. Optional field boundary polygons are supported for visualizing progress, and data can include photos and equipment notes. The app is designed to support both short-term operational planning and long-term tillage recordkeeping.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Cloud-based tillage management app requiring stable internet access.)

OpenATK Rock App (OpenATK, 2025): The OpenATK Rock App is an Android application that allows farm operators to mark the GPS location of rocks encountered in the field for later removal. The app shares marked locations in real time with other workers and devices using cloud storage, ensuring quick response and minimizing the risk of equipment damage. Rocks can be flagged with details such as pickup status, photos, and comments. Once removed, their status can be updated to “Picked Up.” The app is part of a broader suite of precision agriculture tools focused on improving in-field communication and coordination.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Cloud-based rock management tool requiring constant connectivity.)

OpenATK Soil Mapping (OpenATK, 2025): OpenATK Soil Mapping is a web-based application that uses vector tiling (via geojson-vt) and the Open Ag Data Alliance (OADA) protocol to serve and visualize SSURGO soil maps. The system delivers lightweight, tiled geospatial data to clients for efficient display and interaction, making it suitable for farm-scale analysis and field planning. It is implemented in JavaScript and designed to run in-browser, with integration capabilities for digital agriculture platforms seeking soil data visualization. It supports soil sampling, data collection, and visualization, critical for precision agriculture.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (Can work with limited offline functionality but requires cloud access for full features.)

OpenATK Field Work App (OpenATK, 2025): The OpenATK Field Work App is a web application for monitoring the status of field operations such as planting, spraying, and harvesting. It provides real-time tracking of progress, including calculated acreage remaining per operation. The app optionally syncs field boundaries with Winfield's DataSilo platform and uses the OADA API for interoperability. Designed for in-browser use, it supports interactive data updates using WebSockets and is intended to enhance coordination and decision-making during active fieldwork.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (Some offline capabilities, but cloud sync is required for full operation.)

OpenATK Field Manure App (OpenATK, 2025): The OpenATK Manure App is a mobile application designed to generate accurate, per-load records for manure application on livestock farms. Built with Cordova, it captures user-inputted data to create digital hauling logs and supports Android deployment via downloadable APK. The app's structure includes modules for configuration, platform integration, and plugins, allowing farmers to record key operational details efficiently in the field. It is aimed at improving nutrient management and compliance tracking in manure-based fertilization systems.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (Some local data entry possible, but syncing requires internet access.)

OpenATK Harvest Progress Viewer (OpenATK, 2025): Harvest Progress Viewer appears to be a web application under early development, intended to visualize harvest status across farm fields. The repository contains a basic React and TypeScript project structure but does not include a public README or user documentation. While the application likely aims to support monitoring of harvest progress in real time, its specific functionality, deployment details, and integration features are not yet documented.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (Offline data entry possible, but full functionality depends on cloud connectivity.)

Farmtopia Data Exchange Module (Farmtopia HE project, 2025): The Farmtopia Data Exchange Module provides the core services for agricultural data sharing among stakeholders. It includes a cloud-deployable directory where data providers can register APIs and data consumers can discover and access datasets. The system requires providers to support OpenAPI documentation, OAuth 2.0 authentication, and optionally use RDFS-based data semantics. It is built with Python (FastAPI), PHP, and PostgreSQL, and is deployed using Docker containers. The module supports local development with integration testing scripts and is intended for reuse in small-scale or regional data-sharing contexts such as producer organizations or cooperative groups.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Agricultural data-sharing tool requiring cloud connectivity.)

Farmtopia Digital Field Book (Farmtopia HE project, 2025): The Farmtopia Digital Field Book is a web-based tool designed to support small farms in capturing and managing records of field activities, observations, and resource usage. It enables structured logging of actions such as planting, irrigation, pesticide applications, pest scouting, and phenological stages, while also tracking parcel characteristics and assets. The system is deployed using Docker and includes web and API interfaces, access control, and JSON-LD-based data models for semantic interoperability. Data entered is accessible for reuse via API, supporting traceability and integration with external systems.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (Some offline data collection possible, but cloud syncing is required.)

Soilmate (Open Source Agriculture, 2021): Soilmate is a mobile app designed to streamline the collection of soil data at field sampling locations. Built with Flutter, it enables users to log soil texture data using a simple, field-ready interface. The app targets a wide range of users, including professionals in agriculture,

environmental science, geology, and mining. It supports on-device data entry and visualization, and includes setup instructions for Android deployment via emulator or connected device. The repository is active and welcomes contributions via GitHub.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Cloud-based soil monitoring system requiring continuous connectivity.)

AgML (Project AgML, 2025): AgML is a centralized, open-source framework for agricultural machine learning that simplifies access to public datasets, benchmarks, and pretrained models tailored to agricultural tasks. It supports both PyTorch and TensorFlow backends and includes tools for loading, preprocessing, and augmenting imagery and annotations for deep learning. AgML provides out-of-the-box loaders for segmentation, classification, and detection datasets (e.g., apple flower segmentation), and features modules for synthetic data generation and standard ML pipelines. Designed for research and reproducibility, it also includes experiment tracking and reproducible benchmarks.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Cloud-based AI model requiring real-time data access and internet connectivity.)

OpenFarm (OpenFram, 2025): OpenFarm is a collaborative, open-access platform for farming and gardening knowledge, structured around “Growing Guides” — detailed, user-created documents that describe how to grow specific plants under different conditions. Each guide includes actionable information such as planting schedules, spacing, soil preferences, light requirements, and care routines. Inspired by a mix of Wikipedia and recipe websites, OpenFarm offers an API-accessible, crowdsourced dataset designed to support humans and machines alike in learning how to grow food more effectively.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Online farming and gardening knowledge platform requiring internet access.)

Crop Yield Prediction (Github user: JiaxuanYou, 2025): This project implements a deep learning pipeline for predicting crop yields using satellite remote sensing data. It integrates convolutional and recurrent neural networks (CNN + LSTM) with Gaussian process modeling to generate spatial yield estimates based on temporal patterns in multispectral imagery. The repository includes data preprocessing scripts, model training routines, and visualization tools, with workflows built around data from Google Earth Engine and other open remote sensing sources.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (Can run locally but relies on cloud-based models for accuracy.)

Dro-Matic (Github user: drolsen, 2025): DRO-Matic is a fully automated operating system for managing hydroponic growing systems, designed to simplify nutrient dosing, pH and EC regulation, irrigation, and timing. Built for DIY hydroponic cabinets, the system operates via an Arduino-based controller with an LCD interface and microSD storage. Users can create and manage “crops” — customized programs that automate all aspects of a grow cycle. DRO-Matic supports up to 10 nutrient channels and is scalable from personal gardens to larger vertical farm installations, offering an efficient, low-maintenance approach to precision farming.

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (Operates independently on edge devices, with optional cloud integration.)

ADAPT Toolkit (Ag Gateway, 2025): The ADAPT Toolkit is a .NET-based framework that supports data interoperability in agriculture by providing common models and translation mechanisms between agricultural software systems. Developed by AgGateway, it enables seamless data exchange across platforms by standardizing how agronomic data such as prescriptions, observations, and product applications are structured and shared. The toolkit can be built locally with Visual Studio or .NET CLI and is distributed via

NuGet. It is widely used to ensure compatibility between farm management systems, precision ag software, and external data services.

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (Offline operation possible with occasional internet updates.)

AgIsoStack++ (Open Agriculture, 2025): AgIsoStack++ is a cross-platform C++ library for implementing ISOBUS (ISO 11783) functionalities in agricultural machinery and control systems. It provides modular support for key ISOBUS components including Virtual Terminal (VT), Task Controller (TC), AUX-N, and ISOBUS Shortcut Buttons (ISB), enabling standardized communication between tractors and implements. Designed for both hobbyists and industry developers, it includes support for CAN bus controllers, NMEA 2000 fast packet protocol, and common guidance messages. The library is fully documented, STL-compatible, and intended for seamless integration into embedded or hardware-specific environments.

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (Designed for interoperability and can function locally with occasional updates.)

AgIsoStack-Arduino (Open Agriculture, 2024): AgIsoStack-Arduino is a lightweight adaptation of the AgIsoStack++ library for use with Arduino-based hardware, providing ISOBUS (ISO 11783) and SAE J1939 CAN communication functionality. It supports features such as address claiming, virtual terminal (VT) client, task controller client, guidance messaging, and fast packet transport — primarily targeting Teensy boards with future support planned for ESP32. Designed for embedded systems, it enables agricultural machines and implements to communicate seamlessly on off-highway vehicle networks using standardized protocols.

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (Runs on Arduino-based systems with no continuous connectivity required.)

Fields2Cover (Mier, G., et. al. 2023): Fields2Cover is a modular C++ library for generating efficient coverage paths for autonomous agricultural vehicles. It supports advanced Coverage Path Planning (CPP) techniques tailored for field operations such as spraying, mowing, or tillage. The library implements decomposition algorithms (e.g., trapezoidal, boustrophedon) to manage complex and non-convex fields, and includes route optimization tools using Google OR-tools. Version 2.0 introduces obstacle support, swath cost optimization, and a flexible API that can be extended for other industries like robotics or surveillance.

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (Local automation processes; cloud connectivity required for software updates.)

AgOpenGPS (AgOpenGPS-Official, 2025): AgOpenGPS is an open-source precision agriculture application offering real-time GPS-based field mapping, automated guidance, and section control for farm machinery. It includes AgOpenGPS for field operation visualization and AgIO as the communication hub to external hardware. The system supports multiple guidance modes (AB line, curve, contour), auto headland turning, and up to 64-section implement control using NMEA GPS input. Designed for DIY and commercial use alike, it integrates with custom PCB firmware and steering systems for low-cost auto-steering and rate control.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Cloud-based mapping and farm management service requiring continuous connectivity.)

Agroclimatology (Github user: brycejohnston, 2025): Agroclimatology is a Ruby client library for accessing solar radiation and meteorological data from NASA's POWER Agroclimatology Web Resource. It allows users to fetch historical data based on geographic coordinates and optional year ranges. The library returns daily radiation metrics, including top-of-atmosphere insolation, surface insolation, and radiative flux, as structured Ruby objects. Designed for developers and researchers, it provides a simple API for integrating agroclimate data into agricultural decision support tools and data pipelines.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Requires internet access for real-time climate data retrieval.)

Evapotranspiration (Github user: brycejohnston, 2025):: Evapotranspiration is a Ruby library for calculating reference crop evapotranspiration (ET_o), also known as potential evapotranspiration (PET), using well-established methods. The library implements the FAO-56 Penman-Monteith model, Hargreaves method, and Thornthwaite method, and includes functions for estimating missing meteorological variables. It is intended for integration into agricultural data pipelines and modeling tools, supporting users in irrigation planning, crop modeling, and agroclimatic analysis.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Cloud-dependent climate data processing requiring continuous connectivity.)

GDAY model (Github user: mdekauwe, 2025): GDAY (Generic Decomposition And Yield) is a C-based ecosystem simulation model that tracks carbon, nitrogen, and water dynamics at the stand scale. It can run at either daily or sub-daily (30-minute) time steps, using different photosynthesis models depending on the resolution. GDAY supports two-layer or SPA-style water balance modules, a CENTURY-based soil decomposition model, and is configurable via INI-style parameter files. It is intended for ecological and agro-environmental research applications and includes example scripts for running simulations and parameter customization using Python.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (Cloud-based fertilization model, but some local simulations possible.)

Cotton Phenology Dataset (Sitokonstantinou et.al., 2023): The Cotton Phenology Dataset by Agri-Hub contains 1,285 in-field observations from 80 cotton parcels in Greece during the 2021 season. It includes phenological stage data, photos, sowing/harvest dates, and matching Sentinel-2 imagery. Designed to support remote sensing and crop monitoring research, the dataset complements a study published in *PLOS ONE*.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Cloud-based dataset requiring internet access for downloading and processing.)

OpenAgri CSM (OpenAgri, 2025): The semantic model acts as an interoperability enabler by providing clear definitions of API concepts. OpenAgri provides a tailored *ontology* (formal semantic data model) that is built on and extending widely recognized agrifood semantic standards, and which provides the semantics for all APIs available in all the services. More info at: <https://horizon-openagri.eu/os-solutions/>

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (Functions primarily offline; requires occasional internet access for updates or integration with external systems.)

OpenAgri Gatekeeper (OpenAgri, 2025): The “OpenAgri Gatekeeper” serves as an API Gateway with centralised authentication, ensuring secure, efficient, and seamless centralised data exchange between the services in the OpenAgri ecosystem and third-party services. The Gatekeeper responses uses JSON-LD with the OpenAgri Semantic Model to ensure compatibility with modularised and evolving solutions for the agrifood sector, and is deployable on both Edge or Cloud to enable the data sharing through harmonised access to webservices in areas with limited connectivity. It reuses open standards and tools that avoid vendor lock-in, and therefore ensures that the stakeholders maintain full autonomy over their data sharing process. More info at: <https://horizon-openagri.eu/os-solutions/>

Connectivity Requirements: Moderate (Requires regular internet access for authentication and data exchange; some functionalities are available offline.)

3.3.2. IoT Integration & Data Processing and Analytics components

This subsection presents a curated set of open-source components that support the integration, communication, and analysis of data from IoT devices used in agriculture. These tools are essential for developers building precision agriculture solutions, enabling seamless data flow from sensors and devices, efficient data handling, and meaningful insights through analytics and visualization. The IoT integration components include tools for device communication, management, and orchestration—such as FIWARE building blocks, Node-RED, and Mosquitto—which ensure reliable and scalable interactions between physical devices and digital platforms. The data processing and analytics tools—like InfluxDB, Grafana, and Prometheus—enable storage, querying, and visualization of agricultural data to support real-time monitoring and decision-making. Connectivity requirements vary, with some tools designed for local (edge) use and others built for cloud-based deployments requiring constant internet access. Together, these components offer developers a modular and flexible toolkit to design and implement intelligent Agricultural Digital Solutions tailored to different technical and environmental conditions.

Fiware – Wilma (FIWARE Foundation, 2025): Wilma is a Policy Enforcement Point (PEP) proxy component within the FIWARE architecture, designed to secure access to REST APIs and microservices. It mediates all incoming HTTP requests, validating user credentials and enforcing access control policies by integrating with Identity Management (Keyrock) and Authorization PDPs (such as AuthzForce). Wilma is deployed as a Node.js service and supports OAuth2-based authentication. It is used to protect backend services and ensure secure, standards-based interactions in IoT and smart agriculture deployments.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Cloud-based IoT integration; requires constant internet access.)

Fiware – Cosmos (FIWARE Foundation, 2025): Cosmos is FIWARE's Big Data Analysis Generic Enabler (GE), designed to facilitate both batch and streaming processing of context data from IoT and smart systems. It integrates with popular Big Data platforms like Apache Spark and Apache Flink through dedicated connectors, enabling real-time analytics and predictive modeling. Cosmos supports NGSI-v2 and NGSI-LD data formats, making it suitable for various domains, including agriculture, where analyzing large-scale sensor data is crucial. The platform includes components for data ingestion, processing, and storage, and is licensed under AGPL-3.0.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Cloud-based big data analysis for IoT; requires continuous connectivity.)

Fiware - Backend Device Management – IDAS (FIWARE Foundation, 2025): IDAS (IoT Devices API and Services) is FIWARE's reference implementation of the Backend Device Management Generic Enabler. It comprises a suite of IoT Agents that facilitate the integration of diverse IoT devices and protocols into the FIWARE ecosystem by translating device-specific data into the NGSI standard format used by FIWARE Context Brokers like Orion.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Cloud-based device management requiring continuous connectivity.)

Fiware – ORION (FIWARE Foundation, 2025): The Orion Context Broker is the core component of the FIWARE platform, enabling real-time management of context information across smart applications. It implements the NGSI-v2 (and optionally NGSI-LD) standard APIs to support updates, queries, and subscriptions to changes in context data. Orion is typically deployed alongside IoT Agents, databases, and analytic engines to build interoperable, scalable smart systems — including precision agriculture, irrigation control, and livestock

monitoring. Developed in C++, Orion is designed for high-performance environments and integrates easily with other FIWARE Generic Enablers.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Cloud-based context broker for IoT requiring real-time internet access.)

Fiware - Keyrock (FIWARE Foundation, 2025): Keyrock is FIWARE's identity and access management (IAM) component, providing OAuth 2.0-based authentication for users and devices. It manages user accounts, roles, permissions, and supports Single Sign-On (SSO) and federated identity across services. Keyrock integrates with other FIWARE security components like Wilma (PEP Proxy) and AuthzForce (PDP) to enforce end-to-end access control. Built with Node.js and Express, Keyrock exposes REST APIs and includes a web-based user interface for managing organizations, users, and applications within smart system architectures.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Cloud-based identity management requiring continuous connectivity.)

Node-Red (Open JS Foundation, 2025): Node-RED is a low-code programming platform for building event-driven applications through a browser-based flow editor. Originally developed by IBM and now hosted under the OpenJS Foundation, it allows users to wire together hardware devices, APIs, and online services using a visual interface. Built on Node.js, Node-RED is widely used in smart agriculture, IoT, and automation setups to integrate sensors, perform data transformation, and trigger actions across systems. It supports a rich plugin ecosystem, MQTT and HTTP endpoints, and can be deployed from edge devices to the cloud.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (Runs on local servers but can connect to the cloud for extended functionality.)

Eclipse Zenoh (Eclipse Foundation, 2025): Eclipse Zenoh is a unified data protocol and infrastructure that seamlessly blends publish/subscribe, distributed storage, queries, and compute into one system. It is designed for extremely efficient communication across edge, fog, and cloud environments, supporting both data in motion and data at rest. Zenoh uses a Rust-based implementation for high performance and low latency, and supports plugins for REST APIs, geodistributed storage management, and security. It is widely applicable in real-time IoT systems, robotics, and smart agriculture, especially where time-sensitive and distributed processing is required.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (Supports cloud and edge, but connectivity is needed for real-time data synchronization.)

Eclipse Mosquitto (Eclipse Foundation, 2025): Eclipse Mosquitto is an open-source MQTT message broker designed for lightweight, efficient communication between devices in IoT and M2M applications. It implements MQTT protocol versions 5.0, 3.1.1, and 3.1, supporting a publish/subscribe messaging model ideal for low-power sensors and embedded systems. Written in C, Mosquitto is highly portable and can run on various platforms, including Linux, Windows, macOS, and embedded devices like Raspberry Pi. Key features include support for SSL/TLS encryption, bridge connections to other MQTT brokers, and tools like `mosquitto_pub` and `mosquitto_sub` for testing and integration.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (requires network access for MQTT client communication; supports both local and cloud deployments)

Contiki (Contiki OS., 2025): Contiki is an open-source, lightweight operating system designed for resource-constrained devices in the Internet of Things (IoT). It supports multitasking, dynamic loading of programs, and includes a built-in TCP/IP stack with IPv6 support, making it suitable for low-power wireless

communication. Contiki's modular architecture and event-driven kernel allow it to run on a variety of hardware platforms, including microcontrollers and legacy computers. It also features the Cooja network simulator for testing and development.

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (requires mesh or wireless network communication; no internet or cloud required)

FreeRTOS (FreeRTOS, 2025): FreeRTOS is an open-source, real-time operating system (RTOS) kernel designed for embedded devices and microcontrollers. It provides essential multitasking capabilities, including task scheduling, inter-task communication, and memory management, enabling developers to build responsive and deterministic applications. FreeRTOS supports over 40 architectures, such as ARM Cortex-M, RISC-V, and x86, and is widely used in various industries, including automotive, industrial automation, and consumer electronics.

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (operates offline by default; network connectivity required when using optional libraries for communication or cloud integration)

MinIO (MinIO, 2025): MinIO is a high-performance, open-source object storage system designed for cloud-native environments. Written in Go and released under the GNU AGPLv3 license, it offers Amazon S3-compatible APIs, enabling seamless integration with existing S3-based applications. MinIO supports a range of deployment scenarios, from single-node setups to distributed clusters, and is optimized for scalability, performance, and data protection through features like erasure coding and active-active replication. Its lightweight architecture and compatibility with container orchestration platforms like Kubernetes make it suitable for various use cases, including AI/ML workloads, data lakes, and backup solutions.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (requires network access for client-server communication; supports both local and cloud deployments)

Streamlit (Streamlit, 2025): Streamlit is an open-source Python framework designed to simplify the creation of interactive web applications for data science and machine learning projects. It enables users to build and deploy data-driven apps with minimal coding, requiring no front-end web development experience. Streamlit supports integration with popular Python libraries such as pandas, NumPy, Matplotlib, and Plotly, facilitating rapid development of dashboards and analytical tools. Applications can be deployed locally or hosted on platforms like Streamlit Community Cloud or Snowflake.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (operates offline for local development; internet required for cloud deployment and sharing)

PostgreSQL (PostgreSQL, 2025): PostgreSQL is a powerful, open-source object-relational database management system (ORDBMS) known for its robustness, extensibility, and compliance with SQL standards. It supports advanced data types, full ACID compliance, and features like multi-version concurrency control (MVCC), making it suitable for a wide range of applications from single-machine setups to large-scale, distributed systems. PostgreSQL's extensible architecture allows users to define custom data types, functions, and operators, and it supports numerous procedural languages, including PL/pgSQL, PL/Python, and PL/Perl. With a strong community and extensive documentation, PostgreSQL continues to be a preferred choice for developers and enterprises worldwide.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (operates offline for local development; network connectivity required for remote access and cloud deployments)

Senslog (Senslog, 2025): SensLog is a server-side platform for ingesting, managing, and publishing sensor data from diverse sources, including environmental, geospatial, and citizen-generated (VGI) observations. Developed as part of the SDI4Apps initiative, it supports a structured data model and provides APIs for integrating sensor networks into geospatial applications. The system supports PostgreSQL/PostGIS for spatial storage, and includes Java and JavaScript components to enable extensible sensor data workflows. SensLog aims to bridge IoT and spatial data infrastructures in smart environments, including agriculture, transport, and environmental monitoring.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Cloud-based IoT data management for livestock, requiring continuous connectivity.)

ThingsBoard (ThingsBoard, 2025): ThingsBoard is an open-source IoT platform that enables device management, data collection, processing, and visualization across edge and cloud environments. It supports industry-standard protocols like MQTT, CoAP, HTTP, and includes robust features such as rule chains, alarms, dashboards, and built-in support for telemetry. With extensions like ThingsBoard Gateway, it integrates legacy or third-party systems using Modbus, OPC-UA, BLE, and LoRaWAN. Frequently used in smart agriculture, ThingsBoard powers solutions for irrigation automation, livestock monitoring, and environment sensing via its drag-and-drop interface and flexible rule engine.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Cloud-based IoT platform requiring continuous connectivity.)

DJI Payload SDK (DJI Dev Team, 2025): The DJI Payload SDK (PSDK) allows developers to build custom payloads for DJI drones by enabling direct communication with the drone's hardware via ports such as X-Port, SkyPort, or other extension ports. It supports development of payload modules such as mapping cameras, megaphones, LIDAR, searchlights, or video analysis platforms. The SDK provides a C-based API for integrating payloads with drone telemetry, video streams, and automated flight controls, and is suitable for applications in precision agriculture, environmental monitoring, and search-and-rescue.

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (Operates on drones and edge devices with optional cloud connectivity.)

EdgeX Foundry (Linux Foundation, 2025): EdgeX Foundry is a vendor-neutral, open-source edge computing platform designed for interoperable and plug-and-play IoT solutions. Built with a microservices architecture, it provides a unified framework for managing device connectivity, data ingestion, processing, and secure communication across diverse edge devices. The platform supports a wide range of protocols (Modbus, MQTT, REST, OPC-UA) and includes SDKs and services for device management, application logic, analytics, and data export. EdgeX is widely used in industrial IoT, smart agriculture, and automated infrastructure, enabling hybrid edge-cloud deployments.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (Designed for edge computing but requires cloud connectivity for full functionality.)

eKuiper (Linux Foundation, 2025): eKuiper is a lightweight and high-performance **stream** processing engine for IoT data analytics at the edge. Designed for use on resource-constrained devices like Raspberry Pi, industrial gateways, and embedded systems, eKuiper enables local data filtering, transformation, and real-time analytics using SQL-based or visual rule configurations. It supports ETL operations, data aggregation, and integration with cloud platforms (e.g., EdgeX Foundry, MQTT, Kafka). Ideal for edge-first applications in smart farming, energy systems, and industrial IoT, it reduces latency and bandwidth usage by processing data close to the source.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (Can run locally but benefits from cloud connectivity for real-time analytics.)

NanoMQ (Linux Foundation, 2025): NanoMQ is an ultra-lightweight and high-performance MQTT messaging broker built for IoT and edge computing. Designed in pure C for maximum portability and speed, it supports MQTT v3.1.1 and v5.0, features fully asynchronous I/O, and excels in low-latency environments with limited hardware resources. NanoMQ extends the NNG messaging library with an embedded actor model, enabling efficient message routing, scheduling, and multi-threading. It is particularly suited for real-time edge analytics in agriculture, industrial IoT, and autonomous systems, where reliable, high-throughput messaging is critical.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (Can work locally with edge-based MQTT, but cloud is needed for scaling.)

InfluxDB (InfluxData, 2025): InfluxDB is a purpose-built time series database optimized for high-throughput ingest and querying of timestamped data — ideal for IoT, edge computing, DevOps, and analytics use cases. Built in Go, it supports the InfluxQL and Flux query languages and provides integrated features like data retention policies, continuous queries, and downsampling. In smart agriculture, InfluxDB is widely used to store sensor readings such as soil moisture, temperature, and irrigation events, powering real-time dashboards and alerts. It integrates with Grafana, MQTT, and Telegraf for seamless edge-to-cloud telemetry pipelines.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (Can operate locally but requires cloud connectivity for data sync and analytics.)

Grafana (Grafana Labs, 2025): Grafana is a powerful open-source platform for observability and data visualization, allowing users to create interactive dashboards from diverse data sources including InfluxDB, Prometheus, PostgreSQL, MQTT, and more. It supports real-time monitoring of metrics, logs, and traces, and is widely used in DevOps, IoT, and agriculture. In agricultural digital solutions, Grafana enables intuitive visual analytics for sensor data (e.g., soil moisture, weather, irrigation events), and integrates well with tools like Telegraf, Mosquitto, or Node-RED to build full-stack telemetry systems.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Cloud-based visualization tool; requires internet access for real-time data monitoring.)

MongoDB (MongoDB, 2025): MongoDB is a widely used NoSQL document-oriented database designed for flexibility, scalability, and ease of development. It stores data in JSON-like BSON format, enabling dynamic schemas and hierarchical data structures ideal for rapidly evolving applications. In agricultural contexts, MongoDB is commonly used in IoT platforms to manage unstructured sensor data, user profiles, spatial field data, and system logs. It supports replication, sharding, and powerful aggregation pipelines, and integrates easily with frameworks like Node-RED, Express, and Grafana for building full-stack digital farming tools.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Cloud-based database; requires internet access for full functionality.)

Ryax-engine (Ryax technologies, 2025): Ryax is an open-source, low-code workflow orchestration engine built to simplify the development and deployment of AI, data processing, and automation workflows. It enables users to design and run scalable pipelines across hybrid environments including cloud, on-premises, and HPC infrastructures. Ryax provides a modular, microservices-based architecture with a web-based UI, serverless runtime, and integration tools for APIs, data sources, and ML models. Common use cases include automated data pipelines, AI model deployment, and smart infrastructure orchestration — with growing applications in agriculture, energy, and scientific computing.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Cloud-based event-driven workflow engine requiring continuous connectivity.)

Prometheus (Linux Foundation, 2025): Prometheus is a leading open-source monitoring and alerting system designed for reliability and scalability in dynamic cloud and edge environments. It collects time-series metrics via a pull model over HTTP, stores them in a high-performance local database, and supports powerful queries through PromQL. Widely used in infrastructure monitoring, Prometheus is also applied in smart agriculture and IoT to monitor system health, sensor states, or energy consumption. It integrates seamlessly with Grafana for visualization and supports exporters for a wide variety of platforms and hardware.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Cloud-based monitoring and alerting system requiring continuous connectivity.)

QGIS (QGIS Development Team, 2025): QGIS is a free, open-source, cross-platform Geographic Information System (GIS) application that enables users to visualize, edit, and analyze geospatial data. It supports a wide range of vector, raster, mesh, and point cloud formats, integrating seamlessly with tools like PostGIS, GRASS GIS, and GDAL. QGIS offers advanced cartographic capabilities, geoprocessing tools, and a robust plugin architecture, making it suitable for applications in agriculture, urban planning, environmental monitoring, and more.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Cloud-based mapping tool requiring internet access for full features.)

GeoServer (OSGEO, 2025): GeoServer is an open-source Java-based server for publishing, editing, and sharing geospatial data using open standards. It supports a wide range of OGC protocols including WMS, WFS, WCS, WPS, and CSW, enabling seamless interoperability across GIS platforms. GeoServer is widely used in environmental monitoring, agriculture, and smart land management systems for serving raster and vector data from formats like Shapefile, GeoTIFF, and PostGIS. It provides a web-based administration interface and REST APIs, making it highly configurable and scriptable for integration into spatial data infrastructures.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Cloud-based geospatial data server requiring continuous connectivity.)

Rastervision (Azavea, 2025): Raster Vision is a Python-based deep learning framework for building computer vision models on satellite, aerial, and drone imagery. It supports tasks such as chip classification, object detection, and semantic segmentation with built-in integration for PyTorch. Designed for ease of use and reproducibility, it provides utilities for preparing geospatial data, training models, generating predictions, and exporting geo-referenced outputs. Raster Vision is particularly well-suited for precision agriculture, land use analysis, and environmental monitoring, where spatial context and scale are critical. **GSODR** (rOpenSci, 2024): An API client for Global Surface Summary of the Day (GSOD) weather data, providing access to historical weather data for agricultural analysis.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Cloud-based machine learning for satellite imagery; requires connectivity.)

Open Meteo (OpenMeteo, 2025): Open-Meteo is a free, open-source weather forecast API designed for easy, non-commercial integration of global and regional meteorological data. It offers hourly forecasts, 16-day outlooks, and access to 80 years of historical weather data using models like NOAA GFS, ECMWF IFS, DWD ICON, and others. The API supports marine, air quality, geocoding, and elevation data, all accessible without an API key. Designed for low-latency performance and CORS support, Open-Meteo is ideal for agriculture platforms seeking fast, API-accessible environmental data.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Cloud-based weather service requiring continuous internet access.)

WeeWX (Keffer T., et.al. 2024). WeeWX: WeeWX is a lightweight, extensible weather station data logger written in Python. It collects, processes, and archives data from a wide variety of personal weather stations, supporting output to databases, HTML reports, graphs, and third-party services (like Weather Underground). WeeWX is highly configurable through its template system and supports custom drivers for integration with different hardware models. It is popular among hobbyists, agricultural setups, and rural monitoring projects that require local control, offline operation, and customized data logging in farming environments.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (Can collect weather data offline but needs cloud for sharing and analytics.)

HSlayers NG (HSlayers NG, 2025): HSlayers-NG is a modular, open-source web GIS frontend library built with Angular and OpenLayers. It provides customizable map viewer components, tools for spatial data interaction, and integration with services like WMS, WMTS, WFS, and sensor platforms like SensLog. HSlayers-NG is particularly useful for developing interactive web-based environmental, agricultural, or spatial monitoring applications, offering extensible UI elements, 3D Cesium support, and Vega-based chart visualizations. The platform is well-suited for building tailored, spatial data dashboards.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (Cloud-based but can work with cached data offline.)

(Open)Micka (Micka, 2025): (Open)Micka is a web-based geospatial metadata catalog and editor supporting ISO and INSPIRE metadata standards. It implements OGC CSW 2.0.2 and supports metadata formats such as ISO 19115/19119/19139, GeoDCAT, and ATOM. Micka includes a built-in thesaurus system and can interoperate with external registries. Built in PHP with PostgreSQL/PostGIS backends, the platform allows metadata search, editing, validation, and publishing, making it suitable for managing spatial datasets in domains like environmental monitoring, agriculture, and public data portals.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (Cloud-based geospatial metadata system requiring periodic connectivity.)

3.4. Open Hardware-based Agricultural Digital Solutions

This section presents a diverse range of open hardware-based Agricultural Digital Solutions (ADSs) that embody the principles of openness, accessibility, and adaptability. These solutions include physical devices and prototypes designed to address various agricultural challenges, from irrigation and fertilization to environmental monitoring and livestock management. Unlike software-only tools, these hardware solutions offer tangible, on-farm functionalities that can be built, modified, and deployed by farmers, developers, and researchers. Each solution in the catalogue provides openly accessible schematics, manuals, and in most cases, corresponding firmware or software code.

Fido, the Temperature Alarm that Sends Text Messages (Open Pipe Kit project, 2025): Fido is an Raspberry Pi-based temperature monitoring system designed to send SMS alerts when temperature thresholds are exceeded. The project provides a setup wizard, documentation, and tools to facilitate configuration. It supports both WiFi and cellular models, catering to different deployment environments. The WiFi model operates within 100 feet of an internet source and is expandable up to a mile using a WiFi bridge. The cellular model runs on battery power for weeks and sends text messages wherever there is cellphone reception. While the repository offers essential setup tools, detailed information on sensor specifications and communication protocols is limited. Fido's potential applications in agriculture include monitoring

greenhouse temperatures, managing cold storage, and detecting temperature fluctuations in various settings.

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (Operates independently with SMS alerts; no continuous connectivity needed.)

Seeder Roller Generator for Jang Seeders (Makeshop, 2025): This project provides OpenSCAD code to design and 3D print custom seed rollers compatible with Jang JP-1 push seeders. Users can modify parameters within the script to tailor roller dimensions and well configurations to specific seed types and planting needs. Developed by Ash Watson and Makeshop for FarmHack and Science Gallery Dublin, the tool aims to enhance the adaptability of existing seeding equipment.

Connectivity Requirements: None (Fully offline 3D-printed tool; no connectivity required.)

Rover - Remote Electric Fence Switch by Text Message (Farmhack User: Clayton C., 2025): Rover is an open-source hardware and software solution that enables farmers to control electric fences remotely via SMS. Built on an Arduino platform, Rover allows users to turn fences on or off and receive text alerts about power failures, enhancing farm security and operational efficiency. The system assumes the fence is functional when power is supplied; it does not verify the actual fence status.

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (SMS-based control; requires periodic mobile connectivity.)

Temperature Data Logger (Farmhack User: Jane J., 2025): The Temperature Data Logger is an open-source, Arduino-based device designed for recording and monitoring temperature data in agricultural settings. It utilizes an Arduino Uno microcontroller, an Adafruit data logging shield, and a TMP36 temperature sensor to capture temperature readings, which are stored on an SD card for later analysis. The project emphasizes simplicity and expandability, making it accessible for users new to electronics and programming. Potential enhancements include adding an LCD display or integrating relays to control greenhouse heating systems. This tool is particularly useful for farmers interested in tracking temperature variations in environments like greenhouses or under row covers.

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (Operates locally but may require occasional data transfer.)

Orchard Bird Scare Machines (Farmhack User: Spurlock B., 2025): The Orchard Bird Scare Machines project presents a series of low-tech, electrically operated devices designed to deter birds from small orchards, gardens, and similar agricultural settings. Developed over several years, these machines have demonstrated an effectiveness rate of 90% or better in reducing bird-related crop damage. The designs include rotating masts with cross arms, flailing rope systems, and leaf blower-powered setups that create motion and noise to scare birds. Each device operates on adjustable timers, allowing for varied activation intervals to prevent birds from acclimating to the deterrents. The project is documented with videos and detailed descriptions, facilitating replication and adaptation by other farmers.

Connectivity Requirements: None (Mechanically driven; does not require connectivity.)

FarmBot Genesis (Farmbot, 2025): FarmBot Genesis is a fully open-source farming platform designed for precision agriculture. It automates tasks such as seeding, watering, and weeding within a customizable raised bed using a gantry system and interchangeable tools. The system is highly customizable and suitable for educational, research, and personal use. Comprehensive documentation, including CAD models and assembly instructions, is available to facilitate customization and experimentation.

Connectivity Requirements: Maximum (Cloud-based operation with some edge autonomy; requires periodic connectivity for full functionality.)

Compost Sensor (Farmhack User: Smith K., 2025): The Compost Sensor is an open-source system designed to monitor and record temperature and moisture levels in active compost piles. Utilizing Arduino-compatible Moteino boards, thermistors, and wireless communication modules, it transmits data to a central gateway equipped with a GSM module for remote monitoring. This tool aids small-scale commercial composting operations in quality control and certification processes. Detailed build instructions and code are available on Instructables and GitHub.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (Can function locally but benefits from cloud sync.)

Remote Compost Monitor (Farmhack User: Simmons J., 2025): The Remote Compost Monitor is an Arduino-based educational project developed to teach composting and computer science concepts. Students construct a device that measures temperature and moisture levels in compost piles and transmits the data to a custom-built web application. The project includes comprehensive instructions, materials lists, and source code for both the hardware and the web application, making it suitable for classroom settings. While designed as a teaching tool, it offers a foundation for developing more advanced compost monitoring systems

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (Operates on edge, requires periodic internet access for data retrieval.)

Open Source Wireless Field/Garden Sensor Node (TheAcreLab, 2025): This open-source, solar-powered sensor node is designed for remote deployment in gardens or fields to monitor environmental conditions. It measures soil temperature, air temperature, humidity, luminosity, and soil moisture levels. The project's goal is to provide an affordable solution, with a raw cost intended to be under \$20. As of March 2015, soil and air temperature and humidity sensors are active on all nodes, and they are all solar-powered. A prototype soil moisture sensor has been developed but not yet deployed. Further information and updates are available on the project's blog.

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (Operates independently; data transmission methods not specified).

Grower Bot (Github user: Liseman, 2025): Growerbot is an open-source gardening assistant that monitors soil moisture, temperature, and light levels to help automate plant care. Built around Arduino and Electric Imp platforms, it features modular hardware with custom PCBs and 3D-printable enclosures. The system collects environmental data and can trigger irrigation or send alerts based on user-defined thresholds. The repository includes firmware, hardware schematics, and setup instructions, making it suitable for DIY gardeners and educational projects. While the project is no longer actively maintained, it remains a valuable resource for those interested in building a connected garden system.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (Local automation possible, but cloud sync required for full use.)

Chicken Coop Sensor (TheAcreLab, 2025): The Chicken Coop Sensor is a wireless, solar-powered device designed to monitor ambient temperature and relative humidity inside a chicken coop. Built using components from a soil/garden sensor, it features a 3D-printed enclosure for easy installation. The sensor operates autonomously, requiring only a drill and basic hardware for setup. Future enhancements include external environmental sensing and ammonia detection.

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (Operates independently; data transmission methods not specified).

Auto-fill High Output Temperature Controlled Humidifier (Farmhack User: Callahan C., 2025): This project transforms a 5-gallon bucket into a high-capacity (up to 4 gallons/day) humidifier with automatic refill capabilities. It utilizes a PID controller, thermocouple, heating element, and fan to regulate water

temperature and vapor output, ensuring consistent humidity levels. A toilet fill valve enables automatic water replenishment, making it suitable for applications like crop storage and meat curing. Detailed build instructions and component lists are provided.

Connectivity Requirements: None (Fully automated local control; no connectivity required.)

Livestock Weigh Scales (Farmhack User: Renton T., 2025): This DIY livestock scale utilizes hydraulic rams and pressure transducers to measure the weight of cattle. The system converts hydraulic pressure readings into weight data, which is wirelessly transmitted to a receiver using Moteino microcontrollers. Designed for affordability, the scale can be built for approximately \$500, offering a cost-effective alternative to commercial options. Detailed construction instructions, materials lists, and code are provided to assist in building and calibrating the system.

Connectivity Requirements: None (Operates independently without connectivity.)

Waterer for Rotational Grazing (FarmHack user: benediktdairy, 2025): This low-cost, mobile watering system is designed to support rotational grazing by providing flexible water access for livestock. It utilizes a 30–50' heavy rubber hose connected to a central waterline, leading to a portable tub fitted with a 1" Hudson float valve secured by a PVC bracket. The design minimizes soil compaction and muddy areas around fixed water points, allowing for quick setup in new paddocks. Each unit costs under \$100 in materials and can be easily moved by tipping and repositioning. Future enhancements may include integrating flow or water level alerts.

Connectivity Requirements: None (Mechanical system; does not require connectivity.)

Electronic Flame Weeder System (FarmHack user: Loria K., 2025): This Arduino-based system enhances the safety and efficiency of tractor-mounted flame weeders by automatically detecting flame outages and reigniting the burners. It uses a thermocouple to monitor burner temperature and triggers a spark ignition if the flame is extinguished, such as by wind. The system operates on a 12V power supply and is controlled via a manual on/off switch. Detailed build instructions and supporting materials are provided for replication and adaptation.

Connectivity Requirements: None (Fully mechanical and electrical; no connectivity required.)

ANAVI Gardening uHAT (Anavi Technology, 2025): ANAVI Gardening uHAT is an open-source Raspberry Pi add-on board designed for smart gardening applications. It supports multiple sensors, including capacitive soil moisture sensors, waterproof temperature sensors, and I²C sensors for humidity, light, and barometric pressure. The board features plug-and-play slots, GPIO pins for controlling irrigation systems, and a Microchip MCP3002 analog-to-digital converter. Compatible with any Raspberry Pi model featuring a 40-pin header, it facilitates easy setup without soldering.

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (Operates locally but can connect for updates or remote monitoring.)

Baby Groot (Github user: Sxyther, 2025): BabyGroot is an Arduino-based irrigation controller designed for home and urban gardens. It monitors soil moisture levels and automates watering through a relay-controlled valve system. The project includes Eagle CAD files, firmware, a bill of materials, and user manuals, facilitating easy replication and customization.

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (Functions locally but can connect for additional data processing.)

Customized Automated Resource Regulation and Optimization Technology (CARROT) (Github user: Artemis5010, 2024): C.A.R.R.O.T. is a DIY automated irrigation system that employs a water timer, hose,

inverted watering spike, and zip ties to efficiently manage water delivery in gardens or small-scale agriculture. Designed for simplicity and affordability, it offers a practical solution for resource-conscious growers. The GitHub repository provides documentation and design files to assist users in building and customizing the system.

Connectivity Requirements: None (Fully manual system)

Parametric Open Source Cold-Frame Agrivoltaic Systems (POSCAS) (Pearce J. M., 2021): POSCAS is a modular, open-source cold-frame system designed to integrate semi-transparent photovoltaic (PV) modules for agrivoltaic research and small-scale food production. It enables testing of various PV transparency levels and spectral properties to optimize crop growth and energy generation. The design is parametric, allowing customization of dimensions, tilt angles, and insulation via OpenSCAD scripts. Components can be fabricated using distributed recycling and additive manufacturing (DRAM) techniques, utilizing recycled plastics. POSCAS serves as both a passive cold frame and a platform for automated greenhouse systems.

Connectivity Requirements: None (Mechanical structure with no connectivity needs.)

IoT Agriintelligence LoRaWAN Node (Valente A., et.al., 2020): This open-source LoRaWAN node is designed for agricultural monitoring, featuring four 12-bit ADC channels, one 18-bit ADC channel, an I2C port, and an SDI-12 port. It supports a 3.6V LiPo battery and includes an onboard solar energy management system compatible with 5.5–7V solar panels. The project provides PCB files and documentation for building and deploying the node in precision agriculture applications.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (LoRaWAN connectivity required for remote monitoring.)

Vinduino Soil Moisture Sensor Station (Github user: ReiniervdL, 2025): Vinduino is an open-source Arduino-based system designed for agricultural irrigation management. It utilizes low-cost gypsum soil moisture sensors to monitor moisture levels at various depths and locations. The system supports Wi-Fi and LoRaWAN connectivity for remote data transmission and can control irrigation valves based on sensor readings. Detailed documentation, including hardware schematics and firmware, is available to facilitate construction and deployment.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (Supports Wi-Fi and LoRaWAN for data transmission)

Colubris LoRa Meteorological Station Board (Embarcações, 2025): The Colubris LoRa Meteorological Station is an open-source project designed to monitor environmental conditions using LoRaWAN technology. Based on the ESP32-S2 microcontroller and the SX1262 LoRa module, it is capable of transmitting meteorological data over long distances with low power consumption. The project includes hardware schematics, firmware, and documentation to facilitate construction and deployment.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (LoRa-based data collection with cloud integration.)

Green Detect (Github user: Green-bms., 2025): GreenDetect is an open-source wireless sensor network platform designed for environmental monitoring in areas without internet connectivity. It supports up to 60 sensor nodes communicating via the ESP-NOW protocol to a central computer. The system includes an application for real-time monitoring, alarm detection, animated geographic mapping, and data logging. Hardware components encompass custom PCBs, Arduino-compatible firmware, and solar-powered modules. The project provides comprehensive documentation and design files to facilitate construction and deployment.

Connectivity Requirements: None (Operates independently; no internet connection required)

Iguana (IOW LABS, 2025): Iguana is a versatile LoRa-based sensor platform designed for smart agriculture and urban environmental monitoring. It supports multiple wireless communication protocols, including LoRa, Bluetooth, BLE, Wi-Fi, and RF, enabling adaptability to various IoT applications. The system is compatible with sensors such as the DS18B20 for soil temperature, soil moisture sensors, and ambient humidity and temperature sensors. Additional features include an onboard driver for a small water pump, a real-time clock (RTC) module, an SD card slot for data logging, and an OLED screen for real-time data display. The hardware is designed to be low-cost and suitable for both domestic and industrial applications.

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (Edge computing for soil monitoring, with optional connectivity.)

OpenScout (OpenScout, 2025): OpenScout is a low-cost, open-source mobile robot designed for indoor and outdoor tasks, capable of transporting payloads up to 15 kg. Built on a modular architecture, it integrates ROS (Robot Operating System), OpenCV for computer vision, and supports MQTT for communication. The project includes hardware schematics, firmware, and documentation to facilitate construction and deployment.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (Operates locally but requires connectivity for full data sync.)

Phecda (IOW LABS, 2025): Phecda is an open-source environmental monitoring device designed to measure electrochemical variables such as pH, oxidation-reduction potential (ORP), temperature, dissolved oxygen, and electrical conductivity. It utilizes sensors from Atlas Scientific and is powered by an onboard ESP32 microcontroller, which manages data acquisition and transmission. The device features an RFM95 LoRa module for integration with LoRa or LoRaWAN networks, and includes a microSD adapter and real-time clock (RTC) for offline data logging. An OLED screen provides real-time data visualization. Phecda is adaptable to various IoT applications utilizing Bluetooth, Wi-Fi, or LoRa connectivity.

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (Works independently but can sync with cloud services.)

Twig (JUNIPER GARDEN, 2025): Twig is an open-source environmental sensor platform designed to measure temperature and humidity. Built around the ESP32-C3 microcontroller, it features a compact, overmolded design suitable for outdoor deployment. The project provides KiCad design files, 3D models, gerber files, and a bill of materials to facilitate construction and customization.

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (Edge-based sensing with optional connectivity for remote monitoring.)

Mobile Hop Picker (Callahan C. W., & Darby H. M., 2014): The Mobile Hop Picker is a trailer-mounted mechanical harvester developed to support small-scale hop growers in the Northeastern United States. Designed to process up to two bines per minute, it features a stripping section, dribble belts, and a hydraulic system powered by a PTO pump. The machine was constructed using a steel frame, unistrut channels for adjustability, and components sourced from various manufacturers. While a dedicated open-source repository is not available, detailed design information, including schematics and parts lists, is provided in the project documentation.

Connectivity Requirements: None (Mechanical harvesting; no connectivity needed.)

l'Otomate (CAPÉ, 2025): l'Otomate is an open-source greenhouse automation controller developed by and for members of the CAPÉ (Coopérative pour l'agriculture de proximité écologique). Designed for small to large farms, it enables automated control of greenhouse environments at a fraction of commercial costs. Key features include programmable temperature schedules, independent control of sidewall motors, and management of up to two ventilation systems and two furnaces. The system supports DS18B20 temperature

sensors and a DS3231 real-time clock module. Comprehensive documentation, including code, schematics, and design plans, is available to facilitate construction and deployment.

Connectivity Requirements: None (Operates independently; no internet connection required)

Weedinator (Goat Industries, 2025): A line-following weeding robot for automated weed control. The Weedinator caters to small-scale farmers who prioritize organic farming and environmental sustainability. This robot automates the tedious and labor-intensive task of weeding, which is often both monotonous and costly, potentially tipping wage scales beyond feasible limits for small farms. By taking on these undesirable jobs, the Weedinator helps make small-scale, organic farming more viable and economically sustainable.

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (Autonomous operation with optional connectivity for updates.)

BeagleV Ahead (beagleV-ahead, 2025): BeagleV-Ahead is an open hardware single-board computer based on the T-Head TH1520 SoC, featuring a quad-core XuanTie C910 RISC-V CPU (RV64GCV ISA, 2GHz) and a 4 TOPS INT8 NPU. The repository offers full access to schematics, PCB layouts, and mechanical drawings, supporting hardware transparency and customization. Designed for edge AI and embedded applications, its processing power and flexibility make it suitable for smart agriculture tasks such as autonomous monitoring, machine control, and localized data processing.

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (Operates independently with optional connectivity for updates and remote access).

BG0249_DepthAI_RGB_Camera (Luxonis, 2025): The BG0249 is an open hardware carrier board designed by Luxonis for the Sunny A12N02A IMX378 12MP RGB camera module. It interfaces with BW1094 and BW1098FFC baseboards via a 26-pin 0.5mm pitch FFC connector, transmitting 5V power, 4-lane MIPI CSI-2, I2C, and control signals. The board includes on-board power regulation tailored for the camera module and is provided with comprehensive Altium design files, schematics, and 3D models. Its modular design and high-resolution imaging capabilities make it suitable for agricultural applications such as crop monitoring, plant phenotyping, and precision farming.

Connectivity Requirements: None (no software dependency in the repository)

Open Weather Station (Github user: panchazo, 2025): Open Weather Station (OWS) is an open-source, Arduino-based weather station designed for affordability, stability, and ease of assembly. It measures wind speed and direction, gusts, rainfall, temperature, atmospheric pressure, humidity, and ambient light. Data is transmitted via Bluetooth to an Android device running the companion app, which stores, visualizes, and optionally uploads data to services like Wunderground, Thingspeak, Windguru, or OpenWeatherMap via Wi-Fi or cellular networks. The repository includes complete assembly instructions, schematics, and source code, enabling deployment in remote or resource-limited environments. Its modular, field-deployable design supports agricultural uses such as microclimate tracking, irrigation management, and weather-informed decision making.

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (Operates independently with optional connectivity for data uploads and remote access)

HidroIoT (Github user: AlisonRequena, 2025): HidroIoT is an open-source IoT-based water monitoring system designed to measure and transmit water level data. The project includes hardware schematics, firmware, and documentation, facilitating the construction and deployment of the system. While the repository provides essential design files, detailed information on sensor specifications and communication protocols is

limited. HidroIoT's potential applications in agriculture include monitoring irrigation systems, managing water resources, and detecting flooding conditions.

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (Operates independently with optional connectivity for data transmission).

nRF Connect SDK (Nordic Semiconductor, 2025): The nRF Connect SDK is a software development kit designed for Nordic Semiconductor's nRF52, nRF53, nRF70, and nRF91 Series wireless devices. It integrates the Zephyr RTOS and provides a comprehensive suite of libraries, subsystems, samples, and applications to support development across Bluetooth Low Energy, Wi-Fi, cellular IoT, Thread, Zigbee, and Matter protocols. The SDK is managed using the West tool, with the sdk-nrf repository serving as the manifest repository, coordinating multiple modules and dependencies. Its modular architecture and extensive protocol support make it suitable for developing smart agriculture solutions, including wireless sensor networks, remote monitoring systems, and precision farming applications.

Connectivity Requirements: Medium (Requires internet access for initial setup, updates, and integration with cloud services).

Hyphascope (Github user: h-schaefer, 2025): Hyphascope is an open-source, low-cost, high-resolution imaging device designed for capturing detailed images of hyphae in soil. The system utilizes a digital microscope camera (DMC) with 600× magnification to image soil profiles within a volume of 70 × 210 × 1.5 mm. It supports image resolutions of 640 × 480, 1280 × 960, and 1600 × 1200 pixels, corresponding to 1.30 μm/px, 0.65 μm/px, and 0.52 μm/px, respectively. The repository provides Python scripts for operating the device, including functions for camera movement, focus adjustment, and automated imaging sessions. Its ability to monitor soil fungal structures makes it valuable for agricultural applications such as assessing soil health, studying mycorrhizal associations, and evaluating the impact of farming practices on soil microbiota.

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (Operates independently with optional connectivity for data transfer)

RootMaster (OpenHydroponics, 2025): RootMaster is an open-source hardware controller designed for hydroponic automation, integrating a Raspberry Pi with an STM32G4 microcontroller via CAN-FD (up to 1 Mbit/s). It supports sensors for pH, electrical conductivity (EC), water temperature, air temperature and humidity, and flow rate, along with control outputs for pumps and valves. The system features modular sensor interfaces, allowing compatibility with various probes, including those from Atlas Scientific. Power options include USB Power Delivery and a 12 V barrel jack. The repository provides comprehensive hardware design files and documentation, facilitating customization and deployment in agricultural settings for tasks such as nutrient solution management and environmental monitoring.

Connectivity Requirements: Minimal (Operates independently with optional connectivity for remote monitoring and updates).

4. Interactive Catalogue Development

The interactive catalogue developed within the OpenAgri project, hosted on the OpenAgri website, represents the primary digital output of this task. The first version, launched after the initial analysis of Open Source Agricultural Digital Solutions (ADSs), was designed as a dynamic, searchable interface with filter and browsing functionality tailored to the needs of farmers, advisors, developers, and policymakers. It allows users to explore open-source software and open hardware solutions by agricultural production stage, deployment model (edge, cloud, or mixed), end-user type, and other metadata.

This second iteration significantly expands and refines the content of the interactive catalogue. All new entries, descriptions, and metadata collected through Deliverable D1.5 are now being integrated into the online catalogue, ensuring the platform remains a relevant and up-to-date tool. It continues to serve both as a standalone resource and as the underlying knowledge base of the OpenAgri Decision Support Tool (DST), which will use the catalogue to recommend suitable technologies based on biogeographic and socio-economic criteria. Compared to the first version, the updated catalogue includes richer metadata, improved solution descriptions based on technical documentation, and new variables such as connectivity requirements and licensing status. Each solution's profile now contains practical deployment information, such as whether internet access is required and whether the codebase is clearly licensed for reuse. These refinements were informed by both technical repository analysis and consortium discussions and are critical for making the catalogue a trustworthy tool for practical implementation.

4.1. Format and Structure

Usability is central to the catalogue's design. Visitors to the OpenAgri website can search and filter solutions using a range of parameters, including the type of user, targeted agricultural production step, connectivity requirements, and whether the solution is a complete system or a modular component. Each entry includes a detailed solution profile that provides contextualized technical information: a general description, GitHub repository engagement metrics (stars, forks, last commit), deployment model, and licensing information where available. Solutions lacking an explicit open license are flagged, with a recommendation to contact original developers. Hyperlinked references lead to original repositories, organizations, or individual contributors. Solutions developed by unaffiliated individuals are listed using their GitHub or FarmHack usernames, with direct links to their public profiles. Beyond expanded filtering and metadata, the structure now also supports clearer categorization of software into complete solutions and simpler components, and includes a separate section dedicated to open hardware-based ADSs. A greater emphasis has been placed on informing end-users not just about the technical maturity of a tool, but also its connectivity dependencies—essential for deployment in environments with limited infrastructure. Planned improvements include the integration of user-submitted content, feedback features, and support forums, to further enhance community engagement.

4.2. Dissemination Plan

The updated catalogue will be promoted across OpenAgri's digital channels, including social media posts, newsletters, and featured sections on the project website. Engagement activities are tailored to distinct user groups. For example, social media content will target farmers and farm advisors, while developers and technical audiences will be engaged via open-source communities, and peer-to-peer project networks. Workshops and webinars will continue to introduce the catalogue to policymakers, advisors, and researchers,

showing how it integrates with the OpenAgri DST and supports data-informed decision-making. Consortium members are also encouraged to promote the catalogue in national and regional events, technical conferences, and collaborative projects. User feedback mechanisms are under development so visitors can suggest new solutions, report errors, or recommend updates to solution metadata. This will help keep the catalogue dynamic and community-driven, ensuring it adapts to evolving needs in the field of digital agriculture.

4.3. Timeline and milestones

The updated version of the interactive catalogue, incorporating all new solutions and metadata refinements introduced in this deliverable, is being finalized in May 2025. This marks the second major iteration of the tool, following the initial release in 2024. A third and final comprehensive update is planned for December 2026, in alignment with the conclusion of the OpenAgri project. In the interim, smaller updates will be performed continuously based on inputs from consortium partners, DST integration testing, and pilot project results. Solutions deployed and validated through OpenAgri pilots will be prioritised for inclusion, especially those with detailed geographic or contextual deployment information that can support DST replicability assessment. This ongoing catalogue development is directly connected to Project Milestone 8: “Knowledge Base of the Decision Support Tool in place.” Together with the results of Deliverable D1.2 – Analysis of Biogeographic and Socio-Economic Framing Conditions – Updated Version (due in Month 18, June 2025), the catalogue constitutes one of the two foundational components of the DST’s underlying knowledge base. These two resources will be continuously aligned and updated throughout the project duration to ensure that the DST recommendations are grounded in both technological capabilities and regional applicability.

5. Conclusions

5.1. Summary of findings

This second iteration of the Catalogue of Existing Open Source Agricultural Digital Solutions (ADSs) builds significantly upon the initial version delivered in D1.4. The updated catalogue incorporates new complete OS software solutions, simpler components, and open hardware-based tools, expanding both the technical depth and practical applicability of the resource. A total of 132 software-based solutions and 38 open hardware solutions are now included, with detailed metadata covering connectivity requirements, licensing, end-user profiles, TRLs, and targeted agricultural production steps. Beyond simply adding new entries, the second iteration also involved an extensive re-evaluation and update of all existing records. TRL levels were reassessed, metadata fields such as connectivity dependencies were newly introduced, and GitHub repository metrics (stars, forks, last commit) were updated and expanded. The catalogue now includes significantly improved descriptions for each solution, often with technical details gathered directly from source code repositories. Special attention was paid to refining the solution typology, distinguishing clearly between complete, deployable solutions and simpler components that can be reused or combined by developers. The catalogue now provides better support for Decision Support Tool (DST) integration, with detailed classifications that enable DST modules to tailor ADS recommendations for farmers, policymakers, and developers. One critical insight from this process is the limited availability of contextual metadata for many open-source ADSs—especially concerning their geographic deployment regions, training datasets for AI models, or socio-economic fit. This continues to be a shortcoming for many open solutions and presents a challenge for tools like the DST that rely on such metadata for replicability assessments. Nonetheless, the catalogue already includes several solutions with clear deployment regions (e.g. FaST, Sen4Cap, and pilot-deployed tools) and solutions with a clear universal replicability, and it is expected that solutions from the OpenAgri pilots will further strengthen this dimension. On the licensing side, while many tools include well-defined open licenses such as MIT, GPL, Apache, and AGPL, a considerable number of repositories are lacking explicit license files, creating legal uncertainty for reuse. This issue is especially common in solutions developed by individuals or research projects. While such solutions were still included due to their relevance, users are advised to contact developers directly before replicating or modifying these tools. As a general disclaimer, this catalogue provides informative guidance only, and users should verify licensing independently before implementation. The interactive version of the catalogue, hosted on the OpenAgri website, is now being fully updated to reflect all additions and metadata from this deliverable. The catalogue remains one of the two foundational components of the DST’s knowledge base, alongside the contextual regional data compiled in Deliverable D1.2.

5.5. Next Iteration

Looking ahead, the next iteration of the catalogue will continue to expand and refine the documentation of open-source Agricultural Digital Solutions. Particular emphasis will be placed on identifying additional complete solutions across key agricultural production steps, while also enriching metadata for existing entries—especially in areas such as replicability, deployment region, and dataset provenance. The inclusion of more detailed technical documentation and use case validation will strengthen the relevance of these solutions for integration into the Decision Support Tool (DST).

An important development in future iteration will be the structuring of “building blocks” by grouping simpler software components into functional clusters. These building blocks will support developers in assembling tailored digital solutions for specific types of Agricultural Digital Solutions (ADSs), such as smart irrigation

systems or pest detection platforms. This modular approach aims to enhance reusability, simplify solution development, and demonstrate pathways for component integration. The next phase will also incorporate validated outputs from OpenAgri pilot activities. These pilots are expected to yield practical examples of region-specific deployments and further clarify the operational context and applicability of each solution. As these examples are integrated into the catalogue, they will enhance its capacity to support real-world decision-making. Licensing clarity remains a core concern, and future updates will continue to address the high number of solutions that lack explicit license files. Direct outreach to developers will be pursued where feasible, and the catalogue itself will play an active role in raising awareness among technology providers that open-source designation requires not only a public repository but also a clearly defined license.

The interactive catalogue hosted on the OpenAgri website will continue to be updated as new data and relevant solutions become available through project activities, especially pilot validations and targeted research. Updates will be planned in alignment with the project's major deliverables and milestones. This ensures that the catalogue remains a curated and reliable resource, evolving over time to reflect the most relevant and actionable open-source Agricultural Digital Solutions identified by the OpenAgri consortium. Finally, continued integration with the broader OpenAgri knowledge base—particularly the socio-economic and biogeographic framing conditions detailed in Deliverable D1.2—will support more context-aware deployment strategies within the DST. This alignment, together with the implementation of Milestone 8 ("Knowledge Base of the DST in place"), will ensure that the catalogue remains a robust and impactful tool for the democratization of digital agriculture.

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